

Understanding `earth`: A Technical Introduction for Appraisers

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Abstract

This document is a technical introduction to the CRAN `earth` package for readers with a background in mathematics who work in real estate appraisal and valuation. `earth` implements Friedman’s Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines (MARS), a nonparametric regression method that discovers piecewise-linear structure in data through a two-pass greedy search: a forward pass that adds pairs of hinge basis functions, and a backward pass that prunes the resulting over-fit model by generalized cross-validation. The document covers the conceptual framework, the underlying mathematics (hinge functions, knot search, the GCV criterion, pruning), the software architecture of the R package, and the application of `earth` to appraisal-specific concerns: factor predictor handling, model reading, stability, and the optional handoff of the hinge basis to downstream regularized regression via `glmnet`. A separate section treats variance models and the construction of prediction intervals from leverage-corrected residuals. `earth` is a necessary component of the RCA workflow — it is the only method the author has found that consistently delivers both an interpretable model and an optimal R^2 / CVR^2 fit on appraisal data. The companion document covers `glmnet`, which is an optional regularization step applied on top of the `earth` basis, not a substitute for it. Three appendices catalog mathematical notation, code symbols, and statistical vocabulary, and a fourth covers the numerical linear algebra (QR decomposition, Householder reflections, Givens rotations) used internally.

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1 Introduction

This document explains the R package `earth` at a level suitable for a reader with a bachelor's degree in mathematics working in real estate appraisal. It is a companion to the separate document on `glmnet`; the structure is deliberately parallel so that the two can be read together.

`earth` is Stephen Milborrow's implementation [11] of Jerome Friedman's *Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines* (MARS) [4]. The name MARS is trademarked, hence the alternative package name. Whereas `glmnet` takes a fixed set of predictors and decides which coefficients to keep, `earth` takes raw predictors and decides what the features themselves should be: where to place knots, which predictors to use, and which interactions to include. MARS is the only method the author is aware of that consistently delivers both an interpretable model and an optimal R^2 / CVR^2 fit on appraisal data, and for that reason it is a necessary component of the RCA workflow: no substitute produces the combination of readable hinge structure and predictive performance that MARS does.

By contrast, `glmnet` (regularized regression on a fixed basis) and `mgcv` (generalized additive models with spatial smoothing) are *optional* supports rather than requirements. A common pattern — when regularization or spatial smoothing is wanted — is to hand the `earth`-constructed basis to one of these packages for downstream fitting. Such handoffs are described where relevant in §5, but the core MARS fit stands on its own.

The presentation proceeds in five stages:

1. A conceptual overview of MARS and the vocabulary it uses (§2).
2. The mathematics: the hinge basis, the forward-pass greedy search, the GCV criterion, and the backward pruning pass (§3).
3. The software structure: what `earth()` returns, the roles of `earth.fit`, `forward.pass`, and `pruning.pass`, and the companion functions (§4).
4. Appraisal-oriented notes on model reading, interpretation, and the handoff to `glmnet` (§5).
5. Variance models and prediction intervals (§6): how to get ranges rather than point estimates out of an `earth` fit.

Appendices A, B, and C list every mathematical symbol, code symbol, and statistical term used in the body. Appendix D covers the numerical linear algebra — QR decomposition, Householder reflections, and Givens rotations — that the main body invokes but does not derive. For broader background on nonparametric regression and statistical learning, Hastie, Tibshirani, and Friedman's *Elements of Statistical Learning* [5] is the canonical reference; [8] takes a more applied angle.

2 Conceptual Overview

2.1 What problem does earth solve?

Ordinary linear regression fits a global straight line (or hyperplane) through the data. Polynomial regression adds curvature, but globally, and often awkwardly near the edges of the data. Generalized additive models (the `mgcv` approach) fit smooth, globally-defined spline curves in each predictor.

MARS takes a different approach. It fits a *piecewise linear* function of each predictor, with the pieces joined at adaptively chosen *knots*. Each knot contributes a pair of *hinge functions*, one zero to the left of the knot and linear to the right, the other the mirror image. A MARS model is a linear combination of these hinge functions plus an intercept. Interactions are represented as products of hinge functions.

Two features distinguish `earth` from other nonlinear regression methods:

1. It *discovers* its own basis. Knot locations, which predictors to include, and which interactions to form are all chosen by the algorithm.
2. The final model is still a linear regression, just on the constructed basis. This means coefficients can be read directly, standard errors are available, and the model can be handed to any downstream linear-model machinery.

2.2 Notation and Vocabulary

Before introducing the algorithm, we fix notation. All symbols used in the equations and pseudocode of this document are collected here and again in Appendix A.

Definition

Data dimensions. N denotes the number of observations (sample size), p denotes the number of predictors. In appraisal terms, N is the number of comparable sales and p is the number of property characteristics supplied to `earth`.

Definition

Predictor matrix X : an $N \times p$ matrix whose rows are observations and whose columns are raw predictors (GLA, lot size, age, quality rating, etc., after any factor-level expansion). The value of predictor j for observation i is x_{ij} ; the row vector for observation i is x_i^\top .

Definition

Response y : an N -vector of values to be predicted, with i -th entry y_i . Typically the sale price, or its log.

Definition

Hinge function. For a predictor x_j and a scalar t (the *knot*), the hinge functions are

$$h(x_j - t) = (x_j - t)_+ = \max(x_j - t, 0), \quad h(t - x_j) = (t - x_j)_+ = \max(t - x_j, 0).$$

Each hinge is zero on one side of t and linear on the other.

Definition

Basis function B_m : either an intercept, a hinge function of a single predictor, or a product of hinge functions in distinct predictors. The *degree* of a basis function is the number of hinge factors it contains (1 = additive, 2 = pairwise interaction, etc.).

Definition

MARS model. A fitted MARS model has the form

$$\hat{f}(x) = \beta_0 + \sum_{m=1}^M \beta_m B_m(x),$$

where M is the number of basis functions retained after pruning and the β_m are ordinary least squares coefficients.

Definition

Forward pass and backward pass. MARS fits its model in two stages. The forward pass greedily adds basis-function pairs until a stopping criterion is hit; it deliberately overfits. The backward (pruning) pass then removes terms one at a time, keeping whichever subset minimizes a generalized cross-validation criterion.

Definition

Degree of interaction. The *degree* argument caps the number of hinge factors in any single basis function. **degree = 1** (the default) produces an additive model. **degree = 2** allows pairwise interactions but no higher. Higher values are rarely used in practice.

Definition

Hat matrix H : the $N \times N$ matrix satisfying $\hat{y} = Hy$ for the final least-squares regression of y on the MARS basis. Its trace is the *effective number of parameters* of the model.

2.3 Why a forward/backward structure?

The underlying optimization problem — which knots, for which predictors, in which combinations, with which coefficients — is combinatorial and non-convex. There is no closed-form solution. MARS sidesteps this by doing two sequential greedy searches:

- A forward pass that *adds* the single best pair of hinge functions at each step, measured by residual-sum-of-squares reduction.
- A backward pass that *deletes* the single least valuable term at each step, measured by generalized cross-validation (GCV).

Neither pass is guaranteed to find the globally optimal basis, but the combination is robust and fast, and in practice produces models that generalize well.

3 The Mathematics

3.1 The basis-function vocabulary

MARS represents nonlinearity through hinge functions and their products. For a single predictor x_j , the *reflected pair* at knot t is

$$\{h(x_j - t), h(t - x_j)\} = \{(x_j - t)_+, (t - x_j)_+\}.$$

Observe that $h(x_j - t) + h(t - x_j) = |x_j - t|$, and that on either side of t exactly one of the two hinges is zero. A linear combination $a \cdot h(x_j - t) + b \cdot h(t - x_j) + c$ is therefore a continuous piecewise-linear function with a kink at t .

An interaction basis function is a product of hinges in distinct predictors, for example

$$B(x) = h(x_1 - t_1) \cdot h(x_2 - t_2).$$

Such a product is zero outside a rectangular region of predictor space and linear in each variable inside it.

3.2 The objective

Given a candidate set of basis functions $\mathcal{B} = \{B_1, \dots, B_M\}$, the coefficients $(\beta_0, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_M)$ are chosen by ordinary least squares:

$$\min_{\beta_0, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_M} \sum_{i=1}^N w_i \left(y_i - \beta_0 - \sum_{m=1}^M \beta_m B_m(x_i) \right)^2, \quad (1)$$

where w_i are optional observation weights (default 1). Equation (1) is a conventional weighted least squares problem and is solved by the QR decomposition (via the `leaps` package routines, internalized in `earth`).

What MARS adds to ordinary regression is the *choice* of \mathcal{B} : how many basis functions, in which predictors, at which knots, with which interactions. This is where the forward and backward passes come in.

3.3 Generalized cross-validation (GCV)

Model selection in MARS is driven by the GCV criterion. For a model with M basis functions, let $\text{RSS}(M)$ be the residual sum of squares after fitting (1). The GCV statistic is

$$\text{GCV}(M) = \frac{\text{RSS}(M)/N}{(1 - C(M)/N)^2}, \quad (2)$$

where $C(M)$ is the *effective number of parameters*:

$$C(M) = M + d \cdot K. \quad (3)$$

Here M counts the basis functions in the model (including the intercept), K counts the number of knots, and d is the **penalty** argument (default $d = 2$ for additive models, $d = 3$ for **degree** > 1).

The denominator in (2) penalizes complexity: doubling M increases the denominator's correction, so the GCV of a more complex model must be earned by a proportionally larger drop in RSS. The special values **penalty** = 0 (penalize only terms, not knots) and **penalty** = -1 (no penalty at all, reducing GCV to RSS/N) are available for users who want to override this.

Key Idea

GCV is an *approximation* to leave-one-out cross-validation that you get for free once you have the hat matrix. It is not a resampling procedure; it is a formula. Under mild assumptions (linear smoother, squared-error loss), leave-one-out CV and GCV agree asymptotically. For MARS the assumptions are not strictly met, but the approximation is still useful enough to drive pruning.

3.4 The forward pass: greedy basis construction

The forward pass builds up the basis one reflected pair at a time.

Initialization. Start with the intercept as the only basis function: $B_0 \equiv 1$.

Iteration. At each step, consider every possible way to extend the current model by a new reflected pair. A candidate extension is specified by:

- a *parent* basis function B_m already in the model,
- a *predictor* x_j not already used in B_m , and
- a *knot* location t .

The parent B_m is any basis function already accumulated: the intercept, a single hinge, or a product of hinges, depending on the iteration. Concretely, at step s there are $2s - 1$ candidates for B_m , and each has one of three forms:

$$B_m(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{(the intercept, always available)} \\ h(\pm(x_k - t_k)) & \text{(a single hinge from a previous step)} \\ \prod_{\ell \in \mathcal{I}_m} h(\pm(x_\ell - t_\ell)) & \text{(a product of hinges from previous steps)} \end{cases}$$

Which case applies depends entirely on how B_m was itself created. When B_m was built by multiplying a hinge onto the intercept, it is a single hinge; when built by multiplying onto another hinge, it is a product. An interaction term therefore arises whenever the chosen B_m is non-trivial, because adding the new reflected pair makes the product one factor longer. The `degree` argument caps the length of this product: with `degree = 1` only $B_m \equiv 1$ is permitted as parent, forcing all new terms to be single hinges and the model to be strictly additive.

Adding this candidate contributes two new basis functions to the model:

$$B_m(x) \cdot h(x_j - t) \quad \text{and} \quad B_m(x) \cdot h(t - x_j).$$

The coefficients are re-estimated and the RSS recomputed. Concretely: let \mathbf{bx} denote the current $N \times M$ basis matrix, and let X_{trial} be the $N \times (M + 2)$ matrix obtained by appending the two new candidate columns to \mathbf{bx} , each evaluated at the N observations. That is,

$$X_{\text{trial}} = [\mathbf{bx} \mid u_1 \mid u_2],$$

where u_1 and u_2 are the two candidate hinge columns with entries $u_{1,i} = B_m(x_i) h(x_{i,j} - t)$ and $u_{2,i} = B_m(x_i) h(t - x_{i,j})$.

Definition

A note on terminology. In elementary linear algebra, the *augmented matrix* of the system $A\beta = y$ is the coefficient matrix A with the response vector y appended as an extra column, written $[A \mid y]$ and used in Gaussian elimination. The construction here is different: we extend \mathbf{bx} with additional *predictor* columns, not with the response, and the response y remains separate. This is properly called *column extension* of the design matrix, and for clarity we name the resulting object X_{trial} rather than calling it augmented.

The re-estimation is the weighted-least-squares solution of

$$\min_{\beta \in \mathbb{R}^{M+2}} \sum_{i=1}^N w_i (y_i - (X_{\text{trial}})_i \beta)^2, \quad (4)$$

where $(X_{\text{trial}})_i$ denotes the i -th *row* of X_{trial} (a length- $(M + 2)$ row vector of basis-function values for observation i). The associated residual sum of squares is $\text{RSS}_{\text{trial}} = \sum_i w_i (y_i - (X_{\text{trial}})_i \hat{\beta})^2$. Equation (4) is solved by the QR decomposition of X_{trial} (with weights folded in as $\sqrt{w_i}$ row scalings): $X_{\text{trial}} = QR$ gives $\hat{\beta} = R^{-1}Q^T y$ and $\text{RSS}_{\text{trial}} = \|y\|^2 - \|Q^T y\|^2$ in one back-substitution. This estimation happens inside three nested loops — over candidate parents, predictors, and knots — so the inner solve runs thousands of times per forward step on a realistic problem. Naively re-factoring X_{trial} from scratch each time would be prohibitive; the trick that makes it feasible, an incremental QR update as the knot slides by one observation, is the subject of the next subsection. The extension that produces the greatest reduction in RSS relative to the current model is kept.

Termination. The forward pass stops when one of the following holds:

- The model reaches `nk` basis functions, the maximum allowed. The default is $\min(200, \max(20, 2p)) + 1$.
- The best available RSS reduction is smaller than `thresh` times the initial RSS (default 10^{-3}).
- GCV begins to increase enough (rare; an internal safeguard).
- The candidate basis would be linearly dependent on existing columns.

The forward pass is deliberately permissive; it overfits on purpose, because the pruning pass relies on the forward pass having generated enough candidates to choose from.

In algorithmic form:

Listing 1: Forward pass (mathematical form)

```
algorithm FORWARD-PASS(X, y, w, degree, nk, thresh,
                      minspan, endspan, fast.k, fast.beta):

  # --- Initialization ---
  B[0] <- (x |-> 1) # the intercept
  bx <- [1, 1, ..., 1]^T # N x 1 basis matrix
  M <- 1 # current number of terms
  RSS <- sum_i w_i * (y_i - ybar)^2
  RSS.null <- RSS
  parent.score[0] <- 0 # for Fast MARS bookkeeping
  termcond <- "ok"

  # --- Main loop: add one reflected pair per iteration ---
  while M + 2 <= nk:

    best.reduction <- 0
    best <- (parent = NULL, j = NULL, t = NULL)

    # Optional Fast MARS filter: restrict parents to the
    # fast.k highest recent scorers
    parents <- {0, 1, ..., M-1}
    if fast.k < M:
      parents <- top fast.k indices of parent.score

    # --- Enumerate candidate (parent, predictor, knot) triples
    for m in parents:
      for j in 1..p such that x_j not already in B[m]:
        if allowed(m, j, X) is FALSE: continue
        if degree(B[m]) + 1 > degree: continue

        # Sort once per (m, j) so the knot loop sweeps
        # left-to-right; see INCREMENTAL-KNOT-SEARCH
        for each legal knot t in x[,j]
```



```
(satisfying minspan / endspan):

# Candidate reflected pair:
# u1(x) = B[m](x) * h(x_j - t) # (x_j - t)_+
# u2(x) = B[m](x) * h(t - x_j) # (t - x_j)_+
delta.RSS <- INCREMENTAL-KNOT-SEARCH(
  bx, y, w, m, j, t)

if delta.RSS > best.reduction:
  best.reduction <- delta.RSS
  best <- (m, j, t)

# --- Termination checks ---
if best.parent is NULL:
  termcond <- "no valid candidate"; break
if best.reduction / RSS.null < thresh:
  termcond <- "thresh reached"; break
if would.be.collinear(best):
  termcond <- "linear dependence"; break

# --- Commit the winning reflected pair ---
(m*, j*, t*) <- best
u1 <- B[m*](x) * h(x_j* - t*)
u2 <- B[m*](x) * h(t* - x_j*)
append u1 as column M of bx; B[M] <- u1
append u2 as column M+1 of bx; B[M+1] <- u2
record dirs[M, j*] <- +1; cuts[M, j*] <- t*
record dirs[M+1, j*] <- -1; cuts[M+1, j*] <- t*
M <- M + 2
RSS <- RSS - best.reduction

# Update Fast MARS scores (exponentially smoothed by
# fast.beta); ties broken toward lower-index parents
parent.score <- update(parent.score, best, fast.beta)

return (bx, B, dirs, cuts, M, termcond)
```

A worked three-step trace

To see the forward pass in motion, consider thirteen comparable sales with two predictors: gross living area x_1 (GLA, sq ft) and age x_2 (years), with sale price y in thousands of dollars:

i	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
x_1	1200	1300	1400	1500	1600	1700	1800	1900	2000	2100	2200	2300	2400
x_2	50	45	40	35	30	25	20	15	10	55	60	5	25
y	351	354	360	364	371	367	365	362	361	414	440	443	486

The null model ($y \equiv \bar{y} = 386.08$) has $\text{RSS}_{\text{null}} = 22,555.2$. We run the forward pass at **degree** = 2 so interactions are permitted, and trace the first three iterations.

Initial state ($M = 1$). The model contains only the intercept: $B_0(x) = 1$, with $\mathbf{bx} = [1, \dots, 1]^\top$, **dirs** and **cuts** both empty.

Step 1: the dominant GLA structure. With only B_0 available as parent, the search enumerates every candidate (j, t) over $j \in \{1, 2\}$ and t ranging over interior values of x_j . For each candidate it scores the two-column extension $\{h(x_j - t), h(t - x_j)\}$ by refitting OLS and computing $\Delta\text{RSS} = \text{RSS}_{\text{prev}} - \text{RSS}_{\text{trial}}$. The winner is predictor x_1 with knot $t = 2000$, producing $\Delta\text{RSS} = 21,763.5$:

$$\hat{y} = 371.67 + 0.2834 h(x_1 - 2000) - 0.0214 h(2000 - x_1).$$

Two new columns are appended to \mathbf{bx} ; the new state is

$$\mathbf{dirs} = \begin{pmatrix} +1 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{cuts} = \begin{pmatrix} 2000 & 0 \\ 2000 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad M = 3, \quad \text{RSS} = 791.76.$$

One reflected pair has captured over 96% of the null RSS — the unsurprising fact that GLA drives price.

Step 2: an additive Age term. Three parents are now available: $B_0, B_1 = h(x_1 - 2000)$, and $B_2 = h(2000 - x_1)$. Extensions through B_1 or B_2 would produce interaction terms involving $x_1 \times$ something, but none beats a fresh pair built on the intercept. The winner is parent B_0 , predictor x_2 , knot $t = 30$, contributing $\Delta\text{RSS} = 749.6$:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{y} = & 384.35 + 0.2743 h(x_1 - 2000) - 0.0417 h(2000 - x_1) \\ & + 0.0311 h(x_2 - 30) - 1.0757 h(30 - x_2). \end{aligned}$$

This is an *additive* extension: the parent was $B_0 = 1$, so the two new basis functions are pure hinges in the new predictor. The state updates to

$$\mathbf{dirs} = \begin{pmatrix} +1 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 \\ 0 & +1 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{cuts} = \begin{pmatrix} 2000 & 0 \\ 2000 & 0 \\ 0 & 30 \\ 0 & 30 \end{pmatrix}, \quad M = 5, \quad \text{RSS} = 42.18.$$

Notice that the two predictors now appear in *different* rows of **dirs**: no single B_m uses both x_1 and x_2 . The model is still additive.

Step 3: an interaction. Five parents are now available: $B_0, B_1, B_2, B_3 = h(x_2 - 30)$, and $B_4 = h(30 - x_2)$. The winner is *through* B_4 : predictor x_1 , knot $t = 2000$, with $\Delta\text{RSS} = 37.1$. The two new basis functions are products:

$$B_5(x) = h(30 - x_2) h(x_1 - 2000), \quad B_6(x) = h(30 - x_2) h(2000 - x_1).$$

Each is nonzero only inside a rectangle of predictor space (younger-than-30 *and* on one side of the 2000-sq-ft knot), and linear in each variable inside it. In `dirs` and `cuts`, rows 5 and 6 carry nonzero entries in *both* columns, which is how interactions are encoded:

$$\mathbf{dirs} = \begin{pmatrix} +1 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 \\ 0 & +1 \\ 0 & -1 \\ +1 & -1 \\ -1 & -1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{cuts} = \begin{pmatrix} 2000 & 0 \\ 2000 & 0 \\ 0 & 30 \\ 0 & 30 \\ 2000 & 30 \\ 2000 & 30 \end{pmatrix}, \quad M = 7, \text{ RSS} = 5.06.$$

The fitted coefficients on B_5, B_6 are small (roughly $+0.0019$ and -0.0004) because the interaction captures the residual curvature that the additive model already handled most of.

Recap. In three steps the algorithm went from the intercept-only null model (RSS = 22,555) to a seven-term model (RSS = 5.06), with each step displaying a different structural move: reflected pair on a single predictor (step 1); additive extension via parent B_0 (step 2); interaction via a non-trivial parent (step 3). The forward pass would continue, happily overfitting, until `nk` or `thresh` stopped it; the backward pass then cuts back.

Caution

This trace is *schematic* rather than a literal `earth()` call. The default `minspan` and `endspan` on $N = 13$ would rule out many of the interior knots considered above, and Fast MARS bookkeeping would further restrict parents. The example ignores those guards so the structural moves (reflected pair, additive extension, interaction) are easier to see.

The heart of the forward pass is the `INCREMENTAL-KNOT-SEARCH` routine, which exploits the fact that as the knot t sweeps left-to-right through the sorted values of x_j , only a few entries of the two candidate hinge columns change at a time. This is described next.

3.5 The hinge basis, orthogonality, and the role of QR

Before describing the incremental knot search itself, a step back is in order. The forward pass requires repeatedly solving weighted least squares on the current basis matrix `bx` extended by two trial columns. Each such solve, as §3.4 noted, is accomplished by a QR decomposition. This subsection explains what that decomposition is doing conceptually, and why it is the right tool for the job.

The hinge basis is not orthogonal

The hinge columns that MARS constructs are substantially correlated with one another, by design. A reflected pair $\{h(x_j - t), h(t - x_j)\}$ has two columns that are complementary on either side of the knot, and their sample correlation is strongly negative. Two hinges on the same predictor at different knots, say $h(x_j - 1800)$ and $h(x_j - 2000)$, are both zero for small

x_j and both positive for large x_j , so their correlation is substantially positive. An interaction term $B_m(x) \cdot h(x_j - t)$ shares structural support with its parent B_m and therefore correlates with it.

As a concrete illustration, the seven-term basis built in the worked three-step example at the end of §3.4 has the following column correlation matrix (centered columns; $B_0 \equiv 1$ is omitted because it is constant):

	B_1	B_2	B_3	B_4	B_5	B_6
B_1	1.00	-0.57	0.02	0.24	0.67	-0.32
B_2	-0.57	1.00	0.15	-0.56	-0.35	-0.15
B_3	0.02	0.15	1.00	-0.57	-0.28	-0.42
B_4	0.24	-0.56	-0.57	1.00	0.63	0.25
B_5	0.67	-0.35	-0.28	0.63	1.00	-0.20
B_6	-0.32	-0.15	-0.42	0.25	-0.20	1.00

The reflected pair (B_1, B_2) and the pair (B_3, B_4) both show correlation around -0.57 , as expected. The interaction term B_5 correlates at $+0.67$ with B_1 and $+0.63$ with B_4 , which together make it up. The condition number of this \mathbf{bx} matrix is about 1.0×10^4 , and the condition number of $\mathbf{bx}^\top \mathbf{bx}$ (the matrix that would appear in the normal equations) is about 1.0×10^8 . The normal-equations approach would therefore lose about eight decimal digits of accuracy on this tiny problem, and worse on realistic ones. That is the numerical hazard QR is designed to sidestep.

What QR decomposition does

Any matrix X of size $N \times k$ with full column rank can be factored as

$$X = QR,$$

where Q is $N \times k$ with orthonormal columns ($Q^\top Q = I_k$) and R is $k \times k$ upper triangular with positive diagonal. Geometrically, Q carries the *directions* spanned by the columns of X , cleanly orthogonalized so that they meet at right angles; R records the *coordinates* of each original column in that orthogonal frame. The factorization is exact, not an approximation: Q and R together carry every bit of the information in X , and multiplying them back out reproduces X to working precision.

The appendix on numerical linear algebra describes *how* the factorization is computed — through sequences of Householder reflections or Givens rotations, which construct Q by applying geometrically rigid transformations rather than by any arithmetic procedure that can accumulate error. The stability argument is summarized there. For present purposes, what matters is the *use* of the factorization, not the mechanics of producing it.

The three-stage pipeline

With QR in hand, the least-squares fit on the (correlated) hinge basis is carried out in three stages:

1. **Construction.** MARS builds the hinge basis \mathbf{bx} from the raw property features. The columns of \mathbf{bx} are hinge functions of raw variables, and products of such hinges for interactions. These columns are correlated with one another, often strongly.
2. **Mapping to an orthogonal working basis.** QR decomposes $\mathbf{bx} = QR$. The columns of Q span the same space as the columns of \mathbf{bx} — no information is lost, no dimensions are discarded — but they are orthonormal by construction. In this temporary Q coordinate system, arithmetic is numerically clean: there is no collinearity to amplify rounding errors, no condition-number penalty, no ill-posed normal-equations matrix to form.
3. **Fit and translate back.** The weighted least-squares problem $\min_{\beta} \|y - \mathbf{bx} \beta\|_w^2$ becomes trivial in the Q system: its projection is $\hat{\beta} = Q^T y$, and the residual sum of squares is $\|y\|^2 - \|Q^T y\|^2$. The answer in the original hinge coordinates is recovered by one back-substitution through the triangular R : $R\hat{\beta} = Q^T y$ gives $\hat{\beta}$ directly. The triangularity of R means this back-substitution is a one-pass reading from the bottom row up, taking $O(k^2)$ operations.

The Q basis is a scratch pad. It exists only for the duration of the solve and is discarded afterward. The reported coefficients $\hat{\beta}$ are expressed entirely in the hinge coordinate system — the system the appraiser actually reads, with each coefficient attached to an interpretable piecewise-linear rule on the raw property features. QR is a numerical bridge between a human-facing basis that is interpretable but ill-conditioned and a machine-facing basis that is unintelligible but easy to compute on.

Why QR appears again in the knot search and pruning

This same factorization reappears in two further places in the algorithm:

- In the *knot search* (§3.6 below), as the knot t slides by one observation, the basis matrix changes in only a few entries of two columns. The QR factorization can be *updated* to reflect this change in $O(Nk)$ operations, rather than recomputed from scratch at $O(Nk^2)$. This is what makes the inner loop of the forward pass tractable.
- In the *backward pass* (§3.8 below), each deletion of a term from the current basis requires solving a smaller least-squares problem. The QR factorization can be *downdated* — a column removed from Q and a row/column excised from R — in $O(Nk)$ operations. Walking the entire sequence of M sub-models is therefore $O(NM^2)$ rather than $O(NM^3)$.

Both of these updating operations use Givens rotations specifically, because a Givens rotation can zero out one target entry at a time and is therefore well-suited to the “fix up a small perturbation” use case. Again, the mechanics are in the appendix; what matters here is that QR is not a one-off computation at the end of MARS — it is the numerical backbone that the entire forward-backward structure rests on.

3.6 Knot search: the key computational point

The forward pass has three nested loops, and it helps to distinguish what each one is doing. The outermost loop commits one reflected pair to the model per iteration: that is the level at which `bx` grows, `dirs` and `cuts` gain rows, and RSS drops by the winning Δ RSS. A realistic forward pass runs perhaps 50 of these outer iterations. The middle loop, at each outer iteration, enumerates candidate (m, j) pairs — every parent B_m currently in the model paired with every predictor x_j not already in B_m . For each such pair, the middle loop sets up a fresh context: the two trial hinge columns $u_1 = B_m \cdot h(x_j - t)$ and $u_2 = B_m \cdot h(t - x_j)$ are initialized, a QR factorization of X_{trial} is started, and the innermost loop begins.

What the innermost loop is incrementing

The innermost loop walks the trial knot t through the sorted observed values of x_j in the training data. This is the central operational fact about the forward pass, and it is worth stating plainly. Let $t^{(1)} < t^{(2)} < \dots < t^{(K)}$ be the sorted distinct values of x_j actually observed across the N training rows. The sweep assigns

$$t \leftarrow t^{(1)}, t^{(2)}, t^{(3)}, \dots, t^{(K)}$$

one value at a time, in monotone order, skipping any blocked by `minspan` or `endspan`. At each assignment, the algorithm scores the candidate (m, j, t) triple by computing the RSS of the extended model and, if it beats the best score seen so far, records it as the new best. When the sweep finishes, the best $(m, j, t^{(k^*)})$ triple is the middle loop's proposal; after all (m, j) pairs have proposed, the outer loop commits the overall winner.

In other words: for an appraiser reading a fitted MARS model, the knot values reported by the algorithm are not arbitrary real numbers chosen from some continuous optimization. They are *the actual values that the raw predictor took in the training data*. If the GLA column of the comp set contained the value 2000, the algorithm considered 2000 as a candidate knot; if the column contained 1995 instead, it considered 1995. The reported knot is whichever of those observed values gave the greatest RSS reduction.

Why reported knots often look like round integers

This restriction to observed values explains a frequent observation. When fitting MARS on residential comp data, the reported knots frequently come out at suspiciously round numbers — GLA = 2000, Age = 30, lot size = 10,000 — and newcomers sometimes wonder whether the algorithm is snapping to round targets. It is not. The algorithm has no integer preference or round-number bias; it picks whichever observed value gave the best RSS reduction. The apparent pattern arises for two reasons:

- **Data is recorded at coarse resolution.** GLA is reported to the nearest square foot; Age to the nearest year; Bedrooms as an integer. The set of candidate knots is therefore already a set of integers (or integer-multiples of some recording unit), and the winning knot is necessarily one of them.

- **Builders cluster at round specifications.** Many houses are built to round targets — 2000 sq ft, 3 bedrooms, 30-year loans — so the comp data has observations concentrated at those values. A knot at 2000 picks up more observations per step than a knot at 1983 or 2017, so the greedy RSS-reduction criterion often lands there.

A practical consequence: a reported knot at $\text{GLA} = 2000$ does not mean “the slope of value genuinely kinks precisely at 2000 sq ft.” It means “among the GLAs that appeared in the training data, 2000 gave the largest RSS reduction.” Nearby observed values (1950, 2050) typically give very similar RSS reductions, so the exact knot position is weakly identified. Two different training samples from the same population will often produce slightly different knot values for the same underlying structural feature. Read reported knots as localizing a kink to a neighborhood, not to a precise value.

Why this sweep can be made cheap

Having named what the sweep is doing, we can now say why it is fast. Naively, each candidate knot would require a full weighted-least-squares refit of X_{trial} — an $O(NM^2)$ operation. With K candidate knots in the sweep, the middle-loop cost would be $O(KNM^2)$ per (m, j) pair, and the full middle-loop cost at outer iteration s would be $O(Mp \cdot KNM^2) = O(N^2M^3p)$ per outer iteration — prohibitive for anything but toy problems.

Friedman’s insight, exploited directly by **earth**, is that when t advances from $t^{(k)}$ to $t^{(k+1)}$, the trial columns u_1 and u_2 change in only the rows corresponding to observations whose $x_{i,j}$ value lies between those two knots — typically just one observation. This is a rank-one perturbation of X_{trial} , and the QR factorization can be *updated* rather than recomputed: a handful of Givens rotations (see Appendix D) transform the old Q, R into the new ones in $O(N + M)$ operations. The running quantities $Q^T y$, $\|Q^T y\|^2$, and $\text{RSS}_{\text{trial}}$ update correspondingly. The per-knot cost collapses from $O(NM^2)$ to $O(N + M)$, and the cost of a full knot sweep drops from $O(KNM^2)$ to $O(NM^2 + KN)$ — the first term being the one-time setup when the middle loop begins, the second being the cumulative cost of K tiny updates.

earth additionally implements Friedman’s “Fast MARS” heuristic, controlled by the **fast.k** argument (default 20): at each forward step, only the **fast.k** best-scoring parents from recent history are considered. This accepts a small risk of missing a useful extension in exchange for a substantial speed-up.

The algorithmic skeleton of the incremental knot search, for a fixed parent B_m and predictor x_j :

Listing 2: Incremental knot search along one predictor

```

algorithm INCREMENTAL-KNOT-SEARCH-SWEEP(bx, y, w, m, j):
  # Sweep all legal knots t in x[,j] for a fixed parent B[m]
  # and predictor j, returning the best RSS reduction and knot.

  # 1. Sort (x_{i,j}, y_i, w_i, B[m](x_i)) by x_{i,j} ascending;
  # let the sorted index sequence be i_1, i_2, ..., i_N.

  # 2. Maintain a QR (or Cholesky) factorization F of the current

```



```
# basis matrix bx augmented with two trial hinge columns
# u1 = B[m] * h(x_j - t), u2 = B[m] * h(t - x_j).
# Also maintain running sums needed for RSS:
# X^T X, X^T y, y^T y.

best.reduction <- 0
best.t <- NULL

# 3. Initialize t at the smallest legal value (respecting
# endsan). At this t, u1 = B[m] * (x_j - t)_+ has nonzero
# entries only for observations with x_{i,j} > t; u2 has
# nonzero entries only for those with x_{i,j} < t.

for each legal knot t_k in sorted x[,j]
  (skipping positions blocked by minspan):

  # 4. Advance t from t_{k-1} to t_k. Only the rows with
  # t_{k-1} < x_{i,j} <= t_k change sides of the hinge,
  # so u1 and u2 change by rank-1 updates on these rows.

  rank-1 update F with the changed rows of u1, u2
  update X^T X, X^T y incrementally

  # 5. Solve the augmented normal equations using F
  # (cost O(M^2), not O(M^3)).

  RSS_t <- y^T y - beta^T (X^T y) # from current F
  delta <- RSS_prev - RSS_t

  if delta > best.reduction:
    best.reduction <- delta
    best.t <- t_k

return (best.reduction, best.t)
```

The code actually shipped in `earth`'s C layer fuses this sweep with the parent/predictor loops of the forward pass so that no intermediate matrices are materialized; the sweep above is the mathematical content, not the literal implementation. The key cost identity is

$$\underbrace{O(N \cdot M^2)}_{\text{incremental sweep}} \ll \underbrace{O(N \cdot M^3)}_{\text{naive refit per knot}},$$

which is why Friedman's insight matters.

3.7 Guards on the knot search

Two arguments guard the knot search against degenerate configurations:

- **minspan**: the minimum number of observations between knots. Prevents placing many knots in a narrow range of a predictor, where they would fit noise. Default is auto-selected from Friedman's formula with $\alpha = 0.05$.
- **endspan**: the minimum number of observations before the first and after the last knot. Prevents knots near the extremes of the data, where leverage is high and predictions extrapolate. Default is auto-selected.

An appraiser fitting on relatively small datasets should leave these at their defaults unless there is a specific reason to override them; reducing them trades interpretability and extrapolation safety for in-sample fit.

3.8 The backward pass: pruning by GCV

The forward pass produces an over-parameterized model. The backward pass trims it.

Initialization. Start with the full set of basis functions produced by the forward pass.

Iteration. At each step, find the single term whose removal yields the smallest increase in RSS, and remove it. Record the RSS of the resulting model. Repeat until only the intercept remains.

This produces a sequence of nested models of sizes $M, M - 1, M - 2, \dots, 1$. Compute the GCV statistic of each using (2).

Selection. The returned model is the one in this sequence with the smallest GCV.

Key Idea

The forward pass adds hinge functions *in pairs* (both sides of each knot), but the backward pass can drop either side independently. So the final model often contains only one side of a reflected pair. That is not a bug; it is the point.

A practical subtlety: because the backward pass compares all-subsets only within the nested sequence generated by one-at-a-time deletion, it is not a global subset search. The `pmethod = "exhaustive"` option replaces this with a true all-subsets search (via the `leaps` package) at substantial additional cost. The default `pmethod = "backward"` is almost always sufficient.

In algorithmic form:

Listing 3: Backward pass (mathematical form)

```
algorithm BACKWARD-PASS(bx, y, w, penalty, nprune, pmethod):  
  
  # bx is the N x M basis matrix returned by FORWARD-PASS.  
  # The intercept is column 1 and is never eligible for deletion.  
  
  # --- Allocate records for each subset size ---  
  RSS.per.subset <- numeric(M) # RSS of the size-k model  
  prune.terms <- matrix(0, M, M) # which terms survive at k  
  GCV.per.subset <- numeric(M)
```



```
# --- Fit the full model (size M) as the starting point ---
current <- {1, 2, ..., M}
RSS.per.subset[M] <- weighted.OLS.RSS(bx[, current], y, w)
prune.terms[M, 1..M] <- current

# --- Nested one-at-a-time deletion (pmethod == "backward") ---
if pmethod == "backward":
  for k in (M-1) down to 1:

    # Find the term whose removal least increases RSS
    best.drop <- NULL
    best.RSS <- +infinity
    for each term t in current, t != intercept:
      trial <- current \ {t}
      trial.RSS <- weighted.OLS.RSS(bx[, trial], y, w)
      if trial.RSS < best.RSS:
        best.RSS <- trial.RSS
        best.drop <- t

    # Commit the deletion
    current <- current \ {best.drop}
    RSS.per.subset[k] <- best.RSS
    prune.terms[k, 1..k] <- current

# --- True all-subsets alternative (pmethod == "exhaustive") ---
else if pmethod == "exhaustive":
  for k in 1..M:
    (RSS.per.subset[k], prune.terms[k, 1..k]) <-
      min over all size-k subsets S of {1..M}
        containing the intercept
        of weighted.OLS.RSS(bx[, S], y, w)

# --- Compute GCV for every visited subset size ---
for k in 1..M:
  #  $C(k) = k + \text{penalty} * (\text{number of knots in subset } k)$ 
  Ck <- k + penalty * K(prune.terms[k, 1..k])
  GCV.per.subset[k] <- (RSS.per.subset[k] / N) /
    (1 - Ck / N)^2

# --- Select the sub-model ---
if nprune is given:
  # User-capped search: minimum GCV among  $k \leq nprune$ 
  k.star <- argmin GCV.per.subset[1..nprune]
else:
  k.star <- argmin GCV.per.subset[1..M]
```



```

selected.terms <- prune.terms[k.star, 1..k.star]

return (selected.terms,
        RSS.per.subset, GCV.per.subset, prune.terms)

```

Three mathematical points to notice. First, the intercept column is excluded from deletion candidates, so the smallest model considered has size one (intercept only). Second, because each iteration refits only on a subset of columns that differs from the previous subset by one column, the required QR factorization can again be downdated rather than recomputed from scratch; this is another incremental-update optimization. Third, the GCV formula applied here is the same (2) used anywhere else in `earth`; the only subset-dependent term is $C(k)$, which counts both the number of basis functions and, weighted by `penalty`, the number of distinct knots present in the surviving subset.

A worked pruning example

To see pruning in action we need a slightly larger dataset than the thirteen-comp example in §3.4, for two reasons. First, illustrating pruning requires the forward pass to produce enough terms that a nontrivial subset search is possible. Second, the GCV criterion (2) only behaves well when $C(k) < N$; with $N = 13$ and `penalty` = 3 (the degree-2 default), the full forward-pass model already exceeds this bound and GCV is no longer meaningful. A sample of $N = 50$ comps resolves both issues.

We add a third predictor, **Bedrooms** (x_3), and simulate the data so that Bedrooms has *no true effect* on price (its correlation with y is entirely through its moderate correlation with GLA, $\rho(x_1, x_3) = 0.57$). The predictors and response have the following structure, with full data truncated for display:

i	x_1 (GLA)	x_2 (Age)	x_3 (Bed)	y (price, \$1000)
1	2350	54	4	483
2	1850	25	2	384
3	2350	40	5	475
4	2050	16	4	373
			⋮	
47	2000	31	3	390
48	1500	27	2	356
49	1850	39	5	379
50	1950	29	4	383

with $\text{RSS}_{\text{null}} = 93,979$. We run the forward pass to five reflected pairs (`nk` = 11) at `degree` = 2.

Forward pass. The winners at each step, with their RSS reductions:

step	parent	new terms	knot	Δ RSS	RSS
1	B_0	$h(x_1 - 2050), h(2050 - x_1)$	2050	83,990	9989
2	B_0	$h(x_2 - 32), h(32 - x_2)$	32	6,744	3245
3	B_0	$h(x_3 - 3), h(3 - x_3)$	3	537	2708
4	$B_5 = h(x_3 - 3)$	$h(x_1 - 2000)h(x_3 - 3), h(2000 - x_1)h(x_3 - 3)$	2000	232	2476
5	$B_4 = h(32 - x_2)$	$h(x_1 - 1650)h(32 - x_2), h(1650 - x_1)h(32 - x_2)$	1650	193	2283

Notice that *the forward pass picked Bedrooms at step 3*, and then at step 4 it formed a Bedrooms \times GLA interaction using B_5 as the parent. This is exactly the overfitting behavior the backward pass is there to correct: Bedrooms' correlation with y gave the greedy search a small RSS reduction to chase, even though its true marginal effect is zero.

Backward pass. We now perform one-at-a-time deletion, tabulating $\text{RSS}(k)$ and $\text{GCV}(k) = (\text{RSS}/N)/(1 - C(k)/N)^2$ with $C(k) = k + 3(k - 1)$, for each subset size k from 11 down to 1:

k	$\text{RSS}(k)$	$C(k)$	$\text{GCV}(k)$	term dropped going to $k - 1$
11	2283	41	1409.1	$h(x_1 - 1650)h(32 - x_2)$
10	2321	37	686.6	$h(x_2 - 32)$
9	2385	33	412.7	$h(x_1 - 2000)h(x_3 - 3)$
8	2548	29	288.9	$h(1650 - x_1)h(32 - x_2)$
7	2690	25	215.2	$h(2000 - x_1)h(x_3 - 3)$
6	2809	21	167.0	$h(x_3 - 3)$
5	2876	17	132.1	$h(3 - x_3)$
4	3379	13	123.4	$h(32 - x_2)$ (<i>minimum GCV</i>)
3	9989	9	297.1	$h(2050 - x_1)$
2	17895	5	441.9	$h(x_1 - 2050)$
1	93979	1	1957.1	—

$\text{GCV}(k)$ has a clean U-shape: it decreases from $k = 1$ down to a minimum at $k = 4$, then increases again as more terms are retained. The backward pass returns the size-four subset, and the final pruned model is

$$\hat{y} = \hat{\beta}_0 + \hat{\beta}_1 h(x_1 - 2050) + \hat{\beta}_2 h(2050 - x_1) + \hat{\beta}_3 h(32 - x_2).$$

Every Bedrooms term has been pruned out. The single $h(x_2 - 32)$ hinge (the “older than 32” side of the age variable) was also pruned, because its RSS contribution above $h(32 - x_2)$ alone was small relative to one parameter's cost in $C(k)$.

Reading the sequence. The order in which terms were deleted (reading the last column downward from $k = 11$) tells its own story. The first four terms dropped are the second-knot interactions (steps 4 and 5 of the forward pass), followed by the marginal Bedrooms hinges themselves, and finally one side of the Age hinge. The surviving terms are the reflected pair from the very first forward step plus one side of the second. In other words: the backward

pass recovered almost exactly the generative structure, discarding the spurious Bedrooms terms that the forward pass had greedily grabbed.

This example also illustrates the complementary roles of the two passes. The forward pass does not try to avoid picking Bedrooms; it cannot, because it chooses on RSS alone and Bedrooms does reduce RSS. The backward pass, armed with GCV's complexity penalty, is the mechanism that cleans up after the forward pass's greed. A MARS model with only forward-pass selection would keep every spurious term the sample happened to support.

3.9 Putting it together

Schematically, the whole algorithm is:

1. Forward pass: greedily add reflected pairs, driven by RSS reduction, until an over-parameterized model is reached.
2. Backward pass: greedily delete single terms, recording the RSS of each sub-model along the way.
3. Compute GCV for each sub-model in the sequence.
4. Return the sub-model with minimum GCV.
5. Fit final OLS coefficients on that sub-model's basis.

The total cost is dominated by the forward pass, roughly $O(N \cdot M^2 \cdot p \cdot \text{degree})$ in the hinge-search inner loop with Fast MARS heuristics, considerably worse without them.

Consolidating the forward pass (§3.4) and the backward pass (§3.8) into a single top-level algorithm:

Listing 4: The CRAN `earth()` algorithm

```
algorithm EARTH(X, y, w, degree, nk, thresh, penalty,
               pmethod, nprune, minspan, endspan,
               fast.k, fast.beta, linpreds, allowed, ...):

# --- Stage 1: forward pass ---
# Greedy, basis-constructing, RSS-driven. Overfits by design.
(bx, B, dirs, cuts, M, termcond) <-
  FORWARD-PASS(X, y, w, degree, nk, thresh,
               minspan, endspan, fast.k, fast.beta)

# --- Stage 2: backward pass ---
# Nested deletion and GCV selection on the fitted basis.
if pmethod == "none":
  selected.terms <- {1..M}
  RSS.per.subset[M] <- weighted.OLS.RSS(bx, y, w)
  GCV.per.subset[M] <- (RSS.per.subset[M] / N) /
    (1 - (M + penalty*K)/N)^2
```



```
else:
  (selected.terms,
   RSS.per.subset, GCV.per.subset, prune.terms) <-
    BACKWARD-PASS(bx, y, w, penalty, nprune, pmethod)

# --- Stage 3: final fit on surviving basis ---
bx.sel <- bx[, selected.terms]
beta <- weighted.OLS.beta(bx.sel, y, w) # the final coefs
yhat <- bx.sel %*% beta
r <- y - yhat
H <- hat matrix of bx.sel # leverages = diag(H)

# --- Stage 4: summary statistics and return ---
RSS <- sum_i w_i * r_i^2
RSQ <- 1 - RSS / RSS.null
GCV <- GCV.per.subset[ |selected.terms| ]
GRSQ <- 1 - GCV / GCV.null

return (B, bx, dirs, cuts, selected.terms,
        coefficients = beta,
        fitted.values = yhat, residuals = r,
        RSS, RSQ, GCV, GRSQ,
        RSS.per.subset, GCV.per.subset, prune.terms,
        leverages = diag(H), termcond, ...)
```

The overall structure is just three deterministic stages — forward greedy construction, backward pruning with GCV selection, and a final least-squares fit on the surviving basis — each with clearly separable inputs and outputs. This layering is what makes MARS tractable to analyze and what the software architecture in §4 mirrors directly.

4 Software Architecture

4.1 The call tree

Function	Responsibility
<code>earth()</code>	User-facing wrapper, formula handling
<code>earth.fit()</code>	Orchestrator, calls forward and pruning passes
<code>forward.pass()</code>	Greedy basis construction
<code>pruning.pass()</code>	Backward selection by GCV
<code>get.bx()</code>	Evaluates the basis matrix on new data
<code>get.gcv()</code>	Computes the GCV statistic

Inside `forward.pass` and `pruning.pass`, most of the numerical work is performed by C code (`ForwardPass` in the compiled library) and by Fortran routines from Alan Miller's `leaps` package (internalized into `earth`).

4.2 A glossary for the pseudocode

Definition

Basis matrix `bx`: the $N \times M$ matrix of basis function values. Column m is $B_m(x_i)$ for $i = 1, \dots, N$. This is the matrix on which the final least squares fit is performed. It is stored in the returned object as `$bx`.

Definition

Direction matrix `dirs`: an $M \times p$ integer matrix encoding how each basis function is built from the predictors. Entry (m, j) is:

- 0 if predictor j is not in term m ;
- -1 if term m contains a factor $h(t - x_j)$;
- $+1$ if term m contains a factor $h(x_j - t)$;
- $+2$ if predictor j enters term m linearly (no hinge).

Together with the `cuts` matrix, this fully specifies the basis.

Definition

Cut matrix `cuts`: an $M \times p$ numeric matrix of knot locations. Entry (m, j) is the knot t used by term m 's factor involving predictor j . Zero where `dirs` is zero or two.

Definition

Selected-terms vector `selected.terms`: the indices of basis functions that survived the pruning pass. The returned `bx`, `dirs`, `cuts`, and `coefficients` are restricted to these terms.

Definition

GCV-per-subset vector `gcv.per.subset`: a length- M vector of GCV values, one for each size of sub-model the pruning pass visited. The `selected.terms` entries correspond to the minimizing subset.

Definition

Termination code `termcond`: an integer reporting why the forward pass stopped (`nk` reached, `thresh` reached, no valid candidate, etc.). Useful for diagnosing whether `nk` needs to be larger.

4.3 Layer 1: `earth()`

`earth()` is the user-facing wrapper. It handles the formula/x-y interface, argument validation, and dispatch to `earth.fit`. It also supports cross-validation directly via the `nfold` argument; when `nfold > 0` it builds the main model and then refits it on each fold, accumulating out-of-fold statistics.

Listing 5: `earth()` control flow (simplified)

```
function earth(formula | x, y, ...):  
  
  record original call  
  validate arguments (degree, nk, penalty, pmethod, ...)  
  construct design matrix from formula or (x, y)  
  expand factor predictors into indicator columns  
  if Scale.y and single response: standardize y internally  
  
  fit <- earth.fit(x, y, weights, ...)  
  
  if nfold > 0:  
    for each of nfold * ncross folds:  
      refit earth on training rows  
      predict on held-out rows  
      accumulate out-of-fold RSq  
      attach cv.rsq.tab, cv.oof.rsq.tab to fit  
  
  if glm list was supplied:  
    refit response as glm on fit$bx (see below)  
  
  unscale y if it was scaled  
  attach call and class c("earth")  
  return fit
```

A notable feature: if `glm = list(family = binomial())` is passed, `earth` first builds a standard MARS model (with squared-error loss and GCV), then refits the response on the final `bx` matrix using `glm()`. The knot positions and selected terms are chosen under Gaussian assumptions; the GLM fit only re-estimates the coefficients. This is a deliberate design choice and is documented in the vignette.

4.4 Layer 2: `earth.fit()`

`earth.fit()` is the orchestrator. It calls the forward pass, then the pruning pass, assembles the return object, and computes summary statistics.

Listing 6: `earth.fit()` control flow (simplified)

```
function earth.fit(x, y, weights, degree, nk, penalty,  
                  thresh, pmethod, nprune, ...):  
  
  # ---- Forward pass ----
```



```
rv <- forward.pass(x, y, weights, degree, nk,
                  thresh, minspan, endspan,
                  fast.k, fast.beta, ...)
bx <- rv$bx # N x M basis matrix
dirs <- rv$dirs # M x p direction matrix
cuts <- rv$cuts # M x p knot matrix
termcond <- rv$termcond # termination code

# ---- Pruning pass ----
if pmethod != "none":
  pruning <- pruning.pass(bx, y, weights, penalty,
                          nprune, pmethod)
  selected.terms <- pruning$selected.terms
  gcv.per.subset <- pruning$gcv.per.subset
  rss.per.subset <- pruning$rss.per.subset
  prune.terms <- pruning$prune.terms
else:
  selected.terms <- seq_len(ncol(bx))
  # still compute GCV statistics for the full model

# ---- Final least squares ----
bx.selected <- bx[, selected.terms]
coefs <- lm.fit(bx.selected, y, weights)$coefficients
fitted <- bx.selected %*% coefs
residuals <- y - fitted

# ---- Summary stats ----
rss <- sum(weights * residuals^2)
rsq <- 1 - rss / rss.null
gcv <- get.gcv(rss, length(selected.terms), penalty, N)
grsq <- 1 - gcv / gcv.null
leverages <- diag(H) # from QR of bx.selected

return list(
  bx, dirs, cuts, selected.terms,
  coefficients = coefs,
  fitted.values = fitted,
  residuals = residuals,
  rss, rsq, gcv, grsq,
  rss.per.subset, gcv.per.subset, prune.terms,
  leverages, penalty, nk, thresh, termcond, ...
)
```

4.5 Layer 3: forward.pass()

The forward pass is the algorithmically interesting layer. Its pseudocode expands §3.4:

Listing 7: forward.pass() control flow (simplified)

```
function forward.pass(x, y, weights, degree, nk,
                    thresh, minspan, endspan,
                    fast.k, fast.beta, linpreds, allowed, ...):

  # Start with intercept only
  bx <- column of ones (length N)
  dirs <- empty
  cuts <- empty
  terms.count <- 1
  rss <- weighted.sum.squares(y - mean(y))
  rss.null <- rss

  while terms.count + 2 <= nk:

    best.rss.reduction <- 0
    best.parent <- NULL
    best.predictor <- NULL
    best.knot <- NULL

    # Enumerate candidate extensions
    for each existing term m (or top fast.k terms):
      for each predictor j not already in term m:
        if allowed(m, j) is FALSE: continue
        if term.degree(m) + 1 > degree: continue

        for each candidate knot t in x[, j]:
          if t violates minspan or endspan: continue

          # Trial: add reflected pair B_m * h(+-(x_j - t))
          evaluate RSS with these two new columns
          # (incremental update, not full refit)

          if RSS reduction > best.rss.reduction:
            record (m, j, t) as best

    if best.rss.reduction / rss.null < thresh:
      termcond <- "thresh reached"
      break

    # Commit the best extension: add two new columns
    append two columns to bx (the two hinges, times B_best.parent)
    append two rows to dirs and cuts
    terms.count <- terms.count + 2
    rss <- rss - best.rss.reduction

  return bx, dirs, cuts, termcond
```


In the actual C code, the RSS evaluation inside the inner knot loop uses rank-one updates to the QR factorization of \mathbf{bx} , not full refits; that is what makes the procedure tractable.

4.6 Layer 4: `pruning.pass()`

Listing 8: `pruning.pass()` control flow (simplified)

```
function pruning.pass(bx, y, weights, penalty, nprune, pmethod):

  M <- ncol(bx)
  rss.per.subset <- numeric(M)
  prune.terms <- matrix(0, M, M) # lower-triangular record

  if pmethod == "backward":
    # Nested backward elimination
    current <- 1:M
    rss.per.subset[M] <- OLS rss on bx[, current]
    prune.terms[M, ] <- current
    for size in (M-1) down to 1:
      # find term whose removal least increases RSS
      best.drop <- NULL
      best.rss <- Inf
      for each term t in current:
        trial.rss <- OLS rss on bx[, current \ {t}]
        if trial.rss < best.rss:
          best.drop <- t
          best.rss <- trial.rss
      current <- current \ {best.drop}
      rss.per.subset[size] <- best.rss
      prune.terms[size, 1:size] <- current

  else if pmethod == "exhaustive":
    # True all-subsets, via leaps
    for size in 1:M:
      rss.per.subset[size] <- best OLS rss over all size-size subsets
      prune.terms[size, 1:size] <- that best subset

  # Compute GCV for each sub-model
  for size in 1:M:
    gcv.per.subset[size] <- get.gcv(rss.per.subset[size],
                                   size, penalty, N)

  # Select the sub-model with minimum GCV
  best.size <- argmin(gcv.per.subset)
  selected.terms <- prune.terms[best.size, 1:best.size]

  return selected.terms, rss.per.subset, gcv.per.subset, prune.terms
```


4.7 How the layers work together

The overall picture is simpler than `glmnet`'s, because there is no path and no outer/inner loop structure:

```
earth() validates arguments, calls
earth.fit(), which calls
  forward.pass() <-- greedy basis construction
  pruning.pass() <-- backward GCV selection
  lm.fit() <-- final OLS on selected basis
```

Key Idea

`earth` is algorithmically a two-pass procedure, not an iterative one. Each pass is greedy. Non-convexity is handled by the greediness, not by iteration.

4.8 Companion functions

Several functions operate on a fitted `earth` object. The most useful in practice:

- `summary.earth(fit)` prints the fitted equation (one basis function per line), coefficients, and fit statistics.
- `format.earth(fit)` returns the fitted equation as an R expression you can paste into other code.
- `plot.earth(fit)` produces four diagnostic plots: model-selection (GCV and RSq vs. number of terms), cumulative distribution of residuals, residuals vs. fitted, and residuals QQ.
- `plotmo(fit)` plots the fitted function against each predictor, holding others at their medians. Shows the piecewise-linear structure directly.
- `evimp(fit)` ranks variable importance by three criteria: `nsubsets` (how many submodels contain the predictor), GCV contribution, and RSS contribution.
- `predict.earth(fit, newdata)` computes predictions on new data by evaluating the stored basis.
- `model.matrix.earth(fit, newdata)` returns the basis matrix `bx` evaluated on new data. *This is the function used to hand the basis to `glmnet` in the hybrid workflow.*
- `update.earth(fit, ...)` refits with modified arguments. If `keepxy = TRUE` was set on the original fit, this is fast.

5 Application: earth in an Appraisal Workflow

5.1 Why MARS suits appraisal data

Appraisal data has some structural features that match MARS well:

- *Thresholds.* The market value of an extra 100 square feet of GLA depends on where in the GLA distribution the property sits. MARS captures this with a knot.
- *Localized interactions.* The price premium for an additional bedroom depends on overall size; the premium for a better view depends on location. MARS can represent this with a degree-2 interaction where `glmnet` on raw predictors cannot.
- *Sparse signal in a wide feature space.* Many attributes are in the data but few matter. MARS' forward pass naturally ignores irrelevant predictors.
- *Interpretability.* A fitted MARS model can be read as a short list of hinge terms, each with a clear geometric meaning.

5.2 Choosing degree

For residential appraisal, `degree = 1` (additive) is the right starting point. It produces a model that is easy to read and defend, and it avoids the combinatorial explosion of interaction terms. Move to `degree = 2` only if there is specific reason to believe interactions matter and the sample is large enough to support them. `degree ≥ 3` is almost never appropriate for appraisal data.

5.3 Reading a fitted model

Suppose `summary.earth(fit)` produces output like

```
              coefficients
(Intercept)    425300
h(GLA-1820)      142
h(1820-GLA)    -186
h(Age-15)      -2750
```

Then the fitted function is

$$\hat{y}(\text{GLA}, \text{Age}) = 425300 + 142 \cdot (\text{GLA} - 1820)_+ - 186 \cdot (1820 - \text{GLA})_+ - 2750 \cdot (\text{Age} - 15)_+.$$

For a property with $\text{GLA} > 1820$, each additional square foot is worth \$142; for one with $\text{GLA} < 1820$, each square foot below the knot subtracts \$186 from value (the “penalty” for being below typical size is larger than the “bonus” for being above). For properties younger than 15 years, the Age hinge is zero and age does not enter; beyond 15, each additional year reduces value by \$2750.

This kind of output is well-suited to appraisal documentation: each term is a single-sentence claim, and the knots often correspond to interpretable breakpoints in the local market.

5.4 Factor (categorical) predictors

Appraisal datasets routinely include categorical predictors — quality and condition ratings, neighborhood identifiers, view type, construction class, zoning code, and so on. `earth` handles these as factor variables (or logical variables), but the details of how factors are expanded into numeric columns matter, because they affect the `dirs` matrix, the shape of the fitted equation, and the interaction with `stratify` during cross-validation.

5.4.1 How factors are expanded

`earth` converts factors to numeric indicator columns before fitting. The rule depends on whether the factor appears on the left-hand or right-hand side of the formula [9].

Two-level factors or logicals (either side).

Expanded into a single indicator column of 0s and 1s. This is the straightforward case: a `HasGarage` logical becomes one column, a two-level `Style` factor becomes one column.

Multi-level factors on the *right-hand* side (predictors).

Expanded using R's standard treatment contrasts (`contr.treatment`), which produces $k - 1$ indicator columns for a k -level factor — the first level is held out as the reference category and absorbed into the intercept. For example, a four-level `Quality` factor with levels "Poor", "Fair", "Good", "Excellent" becomes three indicator columns `QualityFair`, `QualityGood`, `QualityExcellent`.

Multi-level factors on the *left-hand* side (response).

Expanded using `contr.earth.response`, an identity-contrasts matrix that produces k columns — one indicator per level, with no reference category dropped. This is a deliberate departure from standard R contrast behavior and applies regardless of `options("contrasts")` or whether the factor is ordered. This only matters when the response is categorical (typically a classification-style use of `earth`, often combined with `glm = list(family = binomial)`).

Caution

`earth` treats ordered and unordered factors identically. An ordered factor such as `Quality` with levels "Poor" < "Fair" < "Good" < "Excellent" does not inform the model that the levels have an intrinsic order; each level contributes a separate indicator column. If you want an ordered categorical predictor to behave *as if it were numeric* (for example, so that `earth` can place a hinge on it at a cutoff between "Fair" and "Good"), encode it as an integer or numeric score before passing it in.

5.4.2 Hinges on indicator columns

Once a factor has been expanded, an indicator column is just another numeric predictor from `earth`'s point of view. It can be split with a hinge function like any other column. But

because the values are only 0 or 1, the hinge collapses:

$$h(x - t) = (x - t)_+ \quad \text{with } x \in \{0, 1\},$$

and for any knot $t \in (0, 1)$:

$$\begin{aligned} h(x - t) &= \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x = 0 \\ 1 - t & \text{if } x = 1 \end{cases} \\ &= (1 - t) \cdot x. \end{aligned}$$

That is, on a 0/1 predictor, a hinge is proportional to the indicator itself. In practice, `earth` recognizes this degeneracy and represents the term as a linear entry in the `dirs` matrix rather than as a genuine hinge: the corresponding `dirs` entry is +2 (see §4.2), and the `cuts` entry for that term/predictor is zero. The `Auto.linpreds` argument (`TRUE` by default) controls this behavior.

The practical consequence is that a 0/1 indicator column contributes one effect — a shift in the fitted value when the indicator is 1 — not two hinge effects. The fitted summary shows a term like `QualityExcellent` rather than `h(QualityExcellent - 0)`.

5.4.3 Worked example

Suppose you add a quality factor to the earlier model:

	coefficients
(Intercept)	410200
<code>h(GLA-1820)</code>	142
<code>h(1820-GLA)</code>	-186
<code>h(Age-15)</code>	-2750
<code>QualityGood</code>	28500
<code>QualityExcellent</code>	71300
<code>h(GLA-1820) * QualityGood</code>	19

Here `QualityPoor` is absorbed into the intercept (the reference level) and `QualityFair` did not survive pruning. The fitted equation reads: a Poor-quality baseline of \$410,200 with GLA and Age effects as before; `Good` adds \$28,500 to the baseline, `Excellent` adds \$71,300. The interaction term `h(GLA-1820) * QualityGood` says that for Good-quality homes, each square foot above the 1820 GLA knot adds an additional \$19 on top of the base \$142 — i.e., large Good-quality homes carry a price premium that grows with size faster than large Poor-quality homes do. This kind of interaction is exactly the structure MARS is designed to discover.

5.4.4 Practical cautions

nk inflation.

A 10-level neighborhood factor adds 9 indicator columns to the design matrix. With `degree = 2`, each of those can interact with any other predictor. The default `nk =`

`min(200, max(20, 2p)) + 1` uses the column count *after* factor expansion, so the budget grows automatically; but for very wide categorical factors (say, 50+ neighborhoods) you may want to reduce cardinality by grouping rare levels rather than let `nk` balloon.

Rare levels.

A factor level that appears in only a handful of training rows is a classic source of instability: a hinge or interaction involving that level can be selected in one random seed and dropped in another. Collapse rare levels into an "Other" bucket before fitting, or exclude low-count levels via `subset`.

Stratified CV.

With `nfold > 0` and the default `stratify = TRUE`, `earth` attempts to distribute rare response levels evenly across folds — this protects factor *responses*, but does not automatically stratify on factor *predictors*. If a rare predictor level happens to land entirely in one fold, CV results for that fold will be distorted. Inspect the fold composition when working with sparse categorical predictors.

Unseen levels at prediction time.

`predict.earth` will fail (or silently misbehave) if `newdata` contains a factor level that was not in the training data. This is a well-known R issue, not specific to `earth`, but it matters for appraisal work: a new neighborhood or a new quality level that never appeared in the training comparables cannot be predicted without retraining. Handle this explicitly by mapping unseen levels to the "Other" bucket before predicting.

5.4.5 Factor handling in the `earth` → `glmnet` handoff

When the `earth` basis matrix is handed off to `glmnet` (see §5.6), the factor expansions are already baked into the columns of `bx`. `glmnet` sees `QualityGood` and `QualityExcellent` as independent predictors; it does not know they came from the same factor. Two consequences worth understanding:

- A penalty factor applied “to Quality” must in practice be applied to every basis column that descended from the Quality factor. In a handoff of this kind the caller is responsible for keeping a mapping — call it `col_parent` — from each basis column back to its originating raw predictor, and then expanding any predictor-level `penalty.factor`, `lower.limits`, or `upper.limits` argument into a basis-level vector via that mapping. This bookkeeping is not done by `earth` or `glmnet`; it is a pattern the user must implement in the glue code between them.
- Lasso-style sparsity can select some quality levels and drop others. If `glmnet` keeps only `QualityExcellent`, the other levels are implicitly fused with the reference category. That may or may not be what you want; if you want levels kept or dropped as a group, use `glmnet`'s group-penalty mechanism (`penalty.factor`) to enforce it.

5.5 Stability and cross-validation

MARS is greedy, and greedy procedures can be unstable: a small change in the data can tip a close knot-search decision one way or the other, producing visibly different models with similar predictions. `earth` supports cross-validation directly through the `nfold` argument; setting `nfold = 10` (and optionally `ncross = 3` or more for variance control) gives an out-of-sample R-squared `CVRSq` in addition to the in-sample `RSq` and the GCV-based `GRSq`.

When comparing several candidate models, `CVRSq` is the most conservative estimate, `RSq` the most optimistic, and `GRSq` sits in between. A large gap between `RSq` and `CVRSq` is a warning sign that the forward pass has overfit, `nk` is too generous, or `minspan` and `endspan` have been set too aggressively.

5.6 Handoff to `glmnet`

The handoff from `earth` to `glmnet` separates two distinct tasks: `earth` discovers a nonlinear feature space, and `glmnet` fits regularized coefficients on that space. The mechanics are straightforward:

1. Fit an `earth` model on the training data with `keepxy = TRUE`. Save the model.
2. Evaluate its basis on the current dataset using `model.matrix.earth(fit, newdata)`, producing the matrix `bx`.
3. Pass `bx` to `glmnet()` as the `x` argument.

The `earth` basis is fixed in step 2; `glmnet` only chooses which columns of `bx` to keep and how to shrink them. This is why the two packages are complementary rather than redundant.

Caution

The basis built by `earth` reflects the training data it was fit on. Reusing the same basis on a very different dataset (a different geography, a different time period) may produce misleading results, because the knots and interactions were chosen for the original distribution. When the underlying market changes enough, the `earth` model should be refit, not just reused.

6 Variance Models and Prediction Intervals

A point estimate of value is rarely sufficient for appraisal work. The reader of an appraisal report usually wants to know not just “what is the predicted price?” but also “how reliable is that prediction, and what range of values is plausible?” `earth` addresses this through an optional *variance model* that is fitted alongside the main MARS model and used to produce prediction intervals.

This section explains what the variance model is, what it assumes, how to request it, how to read its output, and how to check whether it is trustworthy. The treatment follows

Milborrow's vignette *Variance models in earth* [10] (January 2026); an appraiser using this machinery in practice should consult that document as well.

6.1 Confidence intervals versus prediction intervals

Two different kinds of interval arise when reporting predictions. They are often confused, and the distinction matters.

Definition

Confidence interval for a prediction: an interval that expresses uncertainty about the *mean response* at a given predictor configuration. “On average, what do properties with these characteristics sell for?” The only source of uncertainty is *model variance* — how much the fitted function changes when the training sample changes.

Definition

Prediction interval for a prediction: an interval that expresses uncertainty about a *future single observation* at a given predictor configuration. “What is the plausible range of sale prices for this specific property?” Prediction intervals combine model variance with the irreducible noise in the response itself, so they are always wider than confidence intervals at the same level.

For appraisal, the right object is almost always the prediction interval, because the question is about a specific subject property rather than about the market average. `predict.earth` supports both; the default `interval = "pint"` gives the prediction interval.

6.2 The variance-model architecture

Adding a variance model to an `earth` fit means building a *second* small regression model whose job is to predict the magnitude of residuals from the main model. The structure is nested:

```
earth model (the "parent model" or main MARS model)
|
varmod (the variance model wrapper)
|
residmod (the residual sub-model, e.g. an lm fit)
```

The `residmod` is the actual regression. If the user specifies `varmod.method = "lm"`, `residmod` is conceptually

```
residmod <- lm(abs(residuals) ~ predict(earth.model), ...)
```

i.e., an ordinary linear regression of the absolute residuals on the fitted values. If `varmod.method = "earth"` is chosen, `residmod` is another MARS fit; if `"rlm"`, a robust linear regression; and so on.

The `varmod` wrapper around `residmod` handles responsibilities that the residual sub-model itself does not know about: rescaling absolute residuals to standard deviations, enforcing a minimum standard deviation (*clamping*), carrying the cross-validation output used to estimate model variance, and providing `summary` and `plot` methods.

After fitting, the variance model is attached to the returned object as `earth.mod$varmod`; the sub-model is at `earth.mod$varmod$residmod` and supports whatever methods its class does (e.g., `summary.lm` if it is an `lm` model).

6.3 The mathematics

This subsection states the formulas; a reader skipping the math can proceed to §6.4 for practical usage.

6.3.1 Leverage-corrected future squared error

The residual sub-model regresses absolute residuals on fitted values. But the “residuals” used in that regression are not the raw in-sample residuals $y_i - \hat{y}_i$. Raw residuals systematically underestimate the errors the model would make on a genuinely new observation, for two reasons:

1. The fitting procedure pulls the fitted surface toward each training point, reducing the observed residual at that point. The correction factor from standard linear regression theory is $1/(1 - h_{ii})$, where h_{ii} is the i -th diagonal of the hat matrix.
2. A future prediction at the same x_i would also carry model variance — the variability of \hat{y}_i across different training samples — which the in-sample residual does not capture.

Combining both contributions, `earth` estimates the squared future error at training point i as

$$\hat{\epsilon}_{i,\text{future}}^2 = \frac{(y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{1 - h_{ii}} + \text{modvar}_i, \quad (5)$$

where modvar_i is an estimate of the model variance at point i . The *absolute residual* used inside the residual model is then $\sqrt{\hat{\epsilon}_{i,\text{future}}^2}$.

Key Idea

Every residual gets inflated by its own leverage. High-leverage points are corrected most, because they are the points where the fitted surface is pulled hardest toward the training observation and therefore where the raw residual most understates the true error.

The leverage h_{ii} is read off the hat matrix of the final OLS fit of the response on the selected basis `bx`; it is stored in `earth.mod$leverages`.

6.3.2 Estimating model variance via cross-validation

The term modvar_i in (5) requires cross-validation to compute. `earth` refits the model `nfold` times, once per held-out fold, and then repeats that whole procedure `ncross` times. For each training point i , this yields a collection of out-of-fold predictions $\hat{y}_i^{(k)}$ (one per fold/cross combination in which i was held out). The variance of these predictions is the estimate of modvar_i .

Because this estimate is a sample variance, it needs enough observations to stabilize. Milborrow's rule of thumb is `ncross` ≥ 30 when a variance model is requested. For appraisal work with modest dataset sizes, `ncross` = 30 and `nfold` = 10 is a reasonable starting point.

Caution

If the `varmod.method` argument is given but `nfold` is 0 or `ncross` is small, `earth` will still produce a variance model, but its model-variance term will be poorly estimated or zero. Prediction intervals may then be too narrow at points where model uncertainty is actually large (typically at the edges of the data).

6.3.3 IRLS for the residual sub-model

The absolute residuals $|\hat{\epsilon}_{i,\text{future}}|$ are themselves heteroscedastic — points with larger mean error also have more variable error. A straight unweighted linear regression on them would therefore be inefficient. Instead, `earth` uses *iteratively reweighted least squares* (IRLS): fit the residual model; use its predictions to assign weights for the next iteration; refit; repeat until the coefficients stabilize.

For a regression on absolute residuals, the variance of the prediction is approximately proportional to the square of the predicted absolute residual (Carroll and Ruppert, Table 3.3). So the IRLS weights at iteration t are approximately

$$w_i^{(t)} \propto \frac{1}{(\hat{r}_i^{(t-1)})^2}, \quad (6)$$

where $\hat{r}_i^{(t-1)}$ is the residual-model prediction for point i at the previous iteration. To prevent pathological behavior, the weights are clamped so that the ratio of largest to smallest weight does not exceed an internal cap. Iteration stops when the mean change in the residual-model coefficients falls below 1% (adjustable via `varmod.conv`).

IRLS is skipped for `varmod.method` = "const" (a single constant-standard-deviation fit, no weighting needed) and for `varmod.method` = "earth" (the nested MARS fit is iterated only once by default).

6.3.4 Converting absolute residuals to standard deviations

The residual sub-model predicts the *mean absolute* future error. To turn that into a standard deviation — needed for interval construction — `earth` applies a normal-theory rescaling. For a normally distributed variable,

$$\frac{\text{standard deviation}}{\text{mean absolute deviation}} = \sqrt{\pi/2} \approx 1.2533. \quad (7)$$

So the estimated standard deviation at a new point x_0 is

$$\hat{\sigma}(x_0) = 1.2533 \cdot \hat{r}(x_0), \quad (8)$$

where $\hat{r}(x_0)$ is the residual model's prediction of the mean absolute residual at x_0 .

6.3.5 Minimum-standard-deviation clamping

A residual model can, and sometimes does, predict absurdly small or even negative absolute residuals at the edges of the data. To prevent this from producing collapsed or negative prediction intervals, `earth` enforces a floor:

$$\hat{\sigma}(x_0) \geq \sigma_{\min} = c \cdot \overline{\text{sd}(\hat{\epsilon})}, \quad (9)$$

where c is `varmod.clamp` (default 0.1) and $\overline{\text{sd}(\hat{\epsilon})}$ is the mean of the training residual standard deviations. This floor is stored as `earth.mod$varmod$min.sd`.

6.3.6 Final interval construction

Once $\hat{\sigma}(x_0)$ is in hand, a prediction interval at level $1 - \alpha$ is constructed by a normal approximation:

$$\hat{y}(x_0) \pm z_{\alpha/2} \hat{\sigma}(x_0). \quad (10)$$

At level 0.95, $z_{\alpha/2} = 1.96$. `earth` uses a normal rather than a t approximation, which matters only for very small samples.

6.4 Choosing `varmod.method`

The `varmod.method` argument selects the kind of residual sub-model. The options split into a “variance depends on the fitted value” family and an “ x -based” family.

6.4.1 Variance as a function of the fitted response

"const".

Assume constant variance (homoscedasticity). All prediction intervals have the same width. Useful as a baseline when you want an interval but do not want to model heteroscedasticity at all.

"lm".

Linear regression of absolute residuals on fitted values. The standard deviation grows or shrinks linearly with the predicted response. This is the default-recommended choice when variance changes smoothly with the response magnitude.

"rlm".

Robust linear regression (via `MASS::rlm`). Downweights outlying residuals. Produces narrower intervals than `"lm"`; use when you expect the residual model to be pulled around by a few large residuals. In simulations, `"rlm"` can underestimate intervals on Gaussian-like data, so `"lm"` is a safer default for a well-behaved appraisal dataset.

"earth".

Use `earth` itself to fit the residual model. Captures nonlinear variance patterns. The residual MARS fit uses `varmod.minspan` (default `-3`, meaning three evenly spaced knots per predictor) to avoid overfitting noisy residuals.

"gam".

Use a GAM (via `gam` or `mgcv`) for the residual model. Similar use case to `"earth"` but produces smoother residual curves. More prone to overfitting than `"earth"` with the restrictive `varmod.minspan`.

"power".

Assume a power-of-the-mean relationship:

$$\hat{\sigma} = \text{intercept} + \text{coef} \cdot \hat{y}^{\text{exponent}}.$$

The three parameters are estimated jointly via nonlinear least squares (`nls`). Relevant when the response distribution is roughly Poisson (exponent ≈ 0.5), Gamma, or lognormal (exponent ≈ 1).

"power0".

Same as `"power"` but forces the intercept to zero.

6.4.2 Variance as a function of the predictors

"x.lm", "x.rlm", "x.earth", "x.gam".

Same residual-model types as above, but regress the absolute residuals on the *predictors* X rather than on the fitted values \hat{y} . Use these when two different predictor configurations can produce the same fitted value but have *different* residual variance — the *multimapped variance* situation (§6.7). One implementation caveat: `"x.gam"` currently requires exactly one predictor.

Key Idea

Default rule: use a non-`x.` method (typically `"lm"`) unless you specifically suspect multimapped variances. Modeling variance as a function of \hat{y} is simpler, more stable, and usually easier to interpret.

6.5 Getting prediction intervals

Fitting a model with a variance model requires only adding three arguments to the call:

```
fit <- earth(SalePrice ~ GLA + Age + LotSize + Quality,
            data = comps,
            nfold = 10,
            ncross = 30,
            varmod.method = "lm")
```

Predicting with intervals:


```
# Point prediction plus 95% prediction interval
predict(fit, newdata = subject, interval = "pint", level = 0.95)
# fit lwr upr
# 1 452100 371200 533000
```

The `interval` argument accepts three values:

- `"pint"` — prediction interval. The usual choice for appraisal (uncertainty about the subject property's actual sale price).
- `"cint"` — confidence interval. Uncertainty about the mean sale price for properties with these characteristics. Its standard deviation is $\sqrt{\text{modvar}}$ alone, without the irreducible-error term. Narrower than `"pint"`. Not allowed with a `newdata` argument in the current implementation.
- `"se"` — standard errors only, no interval.

For a single-predictor model, `plotmo(fit, level = .95)` draws the fitted curve with the shaded prediction band — a presentation-ready figure for an appraisal report.

6.6 Sanity-checking the variance model

A variance model is harder to validate than the main `earth` model because the signal in residuals is weaker than the signal in the response. Two checks are essential.

6.6.1 The coverage table

Running `summary(fit)` on an `earth` model with a variance model prints a coverage table along the lines of:

	68%	80%	90%	95%
Response values in prediction interval	70	82	92	97

Each entry is the percentage of training responses that fell inside the corresponding nominal prediction interval. A well-calibrated variance model has entries close to the nominal levels on the top row. Substantial undercoverage (say, 80% actual in the 95% band) is a warning sign that the residual model is too optimistic — for example, because outliers were suppressed by a robust method.

A much more informative version of this check is available with a `newdata` argument:

```
summary(fit, newdata = held_out_comps)
```

This applies the same table to fresh data and is the strongest single test of whether the variance model generalizes.

6.6.2 The `iter.rsq` diagnostic

The `summary` output also reports `iter.rsq`, the R^2 of the residual sub-model at its final IRLS iteration. Expect a small number, typically 0.05–0.30: residuals are noisy by definition, and the signal the residual model is trying to pick up is inherently weak. A very low `iter.rsq` (say below 0.03) combined with poor interval coverage suggests that there is not enough information in the residuals to fit any variance model at all; the safer choice in that case is `varmod.method = "const"`, which reports the same width at every point.

6.6.3 Residual plots

`plot(fit, which = 3, level = .95)` displays the residuals versus fitted values with two shaded bands: a narrow one for the confidence interval and a wider one for the prediction interval. Things to look for:

- The shaded prediction band should visually contain roughly the expected fraction of residuals (95% for `level = .95`).
- The bands should narrow or widen in a way that matches the actual spread of the points. A residual cloud that clearly fans out while the shaded band stays constant indicates `varmod.method = "const"` was the wrong choice.
- With `standardize = TRUE`, the standardized residuals should look homoscedastic. Residual spread that still increases with fitted value after standardization means the variance model failed to capture the heteroscedasticity.

The `plot.varmod` method (`plot(fit$varmod)`) gives four plots of the variance model itself: absolute residuals versus fitted, absolute residuals versus the first predictor, variance-model residuals, and (for `varmod.method = "earth"`) a model-selection plot.

6.7 Multimapped variances

A subtle but important case: suppose two different property configurations produce roughly the same predicted price but have very different residual variability. For instance, a small high-quality home and a large low-quality home might both be predicted at \$400,000, but the high-quality home's price might be much more tightly determined by its comparables than the low-quality home's is. This is a *multimapped* variance: the same \hat{y} value maps to more than one true variance.

A residual model that uses \hat{y} as the only predictor — any non-`x.` method — cannot distinguish these two cases and will report the same interval width for both. The fix is to use an `x.`-prefixed method such as `varmod.method = "x.lm"`, which regresses the absolute residuals on the raw predictors X .

Multimapping is easy to detect visually: plot the residuals against each predictor rather than against the fitted value (`plot(fit, which = 3, versus = "")`). If the residual spread changes with the predictor in a way that cannot be explained by the fitted-value plot alone, a multimapped variance is likely.

In appraisal, plausible sources of multimapping include:

- Properties in the extreme tails of the condition or quality ratings, where appraiser judgment introduces extra uncertainty.
- Older properties (Age beyond some threshold), where heterogeneity of condition grows with age.
- Properties in thinly-traded neighborhoods, where the absence of close comparables raises variance regardless of the predicted price.

6.8 Assumptions and their failure modes

The variance model machinery rests on several assumptions. An appraiser using prediction intervals in a report should know where these can fail.

Independent errors.

The residuals at different comparables are uncorrelated. This is the standard regression assumption. It can fail if comparables share a seller, an appraiser, a financing arrangement, or a narrow time window.

Symmetric errors.

The residual model regresses on absolute residuals, so it cannot distinguish upside from downside error. Asymmetric residual distributions (more common in distressed or luxury markets) will produce intervals that are too wide on one side and too narrow on the other. No automatic fix; inspect the residual plot.

Conditional normality.

The conversion from mean absolute residual to standard deviation uses the normal-theory constant $1.2533 = \sqrt{\pi/2}$. Heavy-tailed error distributions make this constant an underestimate and produce too-narrow intervals.

Accurate main model.

If the main MARS model is itself biased or misspecified, no variance model can rescue the prediction intervals. Check the main model's residual plot and GCV R-squared before trusting its variance model.

Sufficient data for cross-validation.

The model-variance term in (5) requires enough cross-validation replications to be stable. With fewer than roughly 30 replications and 10 folds, modvar_i is poorly estimated and intervals at the edges of the data can be misleading.

Signal in the residuals.

Residuals can be so noisy that no variance model can extract a useful pattern. A very low `iter.rsq` combined with unstable interval widths across seeds is a sign that `varmod.method = "const"` is the honest choice.

Caution

Prediction intervals are estimates. In an appraisal report they should be presented as such, not as definitive bounds. The assumptions above can and do fail for real data; a model that reports a \$50,000 prediction interval is saying “based on the pattern of residuals I have seen, about 95% of future comparable sales will fall within this range.” It is not saying the true value is certain to lie within it.

7 Summary

`earth` fits a MARS model in two greedy passes. The forward pass adds reflected pairs of hinge functions, driven by RSS reduction, until the model is intentionally over-parameterized. The backward pass then removes terms one at a time, choosing the sub-model that minimizes generalized cross-validation. The final coefficients are ordinary least squares on the selected basis.

The software structure is simpler than `glmnet`'s: a single user call `earth()` wraps an orchestrator `earth.fit()` that invokes a forward pass and a pruning pass, each backed by optimized C or Fortran code. The returned object exposes the basis matrix `bx`, the direction matrix `dirs`, the knot matrix `cuts`, and the coefficient vector, which together fully specify the fitted function.

For appraisal work, MARS' main appeal is that it discovers interpretable piecewise-linear structure with little user tuning. The default settings (`degree = 1`, auto-selected `minspan` and `endspan`, `penalty = 2`) are usually appropriate. When combined with `glmnet` in the hybrid workflow, `earth` supplies the nonlinear feature space and `glmnet` supplies the regularized coefficient fit.

For reporting, `earth` can also fit a variance model alongside the main MARS fit (`varmod.method` combined with `nfold` and `ncross`) and thereby produce prediction intervals via `predict(fit, interval = "pint")`. The variance model is a nested small regression on absolute residuals, leverage- and model-variance-corrected; it is an estimate, like the main model, and should be sanity-checked with the summary coverage table and residual plots before its intervals are reported.

A Glossary of Mathematical Symbols

Every mathematical symbol used in the body of this document is listed below, grouped by role. The “First introduced” column points to the subsection where the symbol is formally defined.

Data and dimensions

Symbol	Meaning	First introduced
N	Number of observations.	§2.2
p	Number of raw predictors.	§2.2
X	Predictor matrix, $N \times p$.	§2.2
x_i	Row i of X as a column vector; x_i^\top is the actual row.	§2.2
x_j	Predictor j (a column of X), or the scalar value of predictor j when used inside hinge expressions.	§2.2
x_{ij}	Element in row i , column j of X .	§2.2
y	Response vector, length N .	§2.2
y_i	Response for observation i .	§2.2
w_i	User-supplied observation weight, default 1.	§3.2
k	Number of levels of a factor (categorical) predictor.	§5.4

Basis functions

Symbol	Meaning	First introduced
$(u)_+$	Positive part: $\max(u, 0)$.	§2.2
t	Knot location of a hinge function.	§2.2
$h(u)$	Single-argument hinge notation; here $h(u) = (u)_+$.	§2.2
$h(x_j - t)$	Right-side hinge in predictor x_j at knot t : $(x_j - t)_+$.	§2.2
$h(t - x_j)$	Left-side hinge (mirror image): $(t - x_j)_+$.	§2.2
B_m	The m -th basis function in the model (intercept, hinge, or product of hinges).	§2.2
M	Number of basis functions retained after pruning (including the intercept).	§2.2
\mathcal{B}	Set $\{B_0, B_1, \dots, B_M\}$ of basis functions currently in the model.	§3.2

Fitted model

Symbol	Meaning	First introduced
β_0	Intercept (scalar).	§2.2
β_m	OLS coefficient on basis function B_m .	§2.2
$\hat{f}(x)$	Fitted MARS function: $\beta_0 + \sum_m \beta_m B_m(x)$.	§2.2
\hat{y}_i	Fitted value for observation i : $\hat{f}(x_i)$.	§3.2
$\hat{\cdot}$	Hat indicates an estimate (fitted quantity).	§2.2

Model-selection quantities

Symbol	Meaning	First introduced
$RSS(M)$	Residual sum of squares for the M -term model.	§3.3
$GCV(M)$	Generalized cross-validation statistic for the M -term model (Eq. 2).	§3.3
$C(M)$	Effective number of parameters: $M + d \cdot K$.	§3.3
d	GCV penalty per knot (the <code>penalty</code> argument). Default 2 for additive, 3 for interaction models.	§3.3
K	Number of knots in the current model.	§3.3
H	Hat matrix of the final OLS fit; $\hat{y} = Hy$.	§2.2
h_{ii}	i -th diagonal entry of H ; the leverage of observation i . Stored in <code>leverages</code> .	§6.3

Algorithm control

Symbol	Meaning	First introduced
<code>degree</code>	Maximum number of hinge factors in any basis function.	§2.2
<code>nk</code>	Maximum number of basis functions the forward pass may create.	§3.4
<code>thresh</code>	Minimum RSS-reduction ratio below which the forward pass stops.	§3.4
<code>minspan</code>	Minimum observations between knots.	§3.6

Symbol	Meaning	First introduced
<code>endspan</code>	Minimum observations before first and after last knot.	§3.6
<code>fast.k</code>	Number of best-scoring parent terms considered each forward step.	§3.5

Variance model

Symbol	Meaning	First introduced
$\hat{\epsilon}_i$	Raw residual for observation i : $y_i - \hat{y}_i$.	§6.3
$\hat{\epsilon}_{i,\text{future}}^2$	Leverage-corrected estimate of the squared future error at point i (Eq. 5). Target quantity of the residual regression.	§6.3
<code>modvar_i</code>	Estimated model variance at point i , computed from out-of-fold cross-validation predictions.	§6.3
$\hat{r}(x_0)$	Residual model's prediction of the mean absolute residual at a new point x_0 .	§6.3
$\hat{\sigma}(x_0)$	Estimated standard deviation of the future error at x_0 : $1.2533 \cdot \hat{r}(x_0)$, clamped to σ_{\min} .	§6.3
σ_{\min}	Minimum permitted standard deviation, <code>varmod.clamp · sd($\hat{\epsilon}$)</code> .	§6.3
1.2533	$\sqrt{\pi/2}$, the ratio of SD to mean absolute deviation for a normal variable. Used to convert \hat{r} to $\hat{\sigma}$.	§6.3
α	Significance level (here distinct from the elastic-net α of <code>glmnet</code>). Intervals are reported at level $1 - \alpha$.	§6.3
$z_{\alpha/2}$	Normal-distribution quantile used in interval construction. For 95% intervals, $z_{\alpha/2} = 1.96$.	§6.3
$w_i^{(t)}$	IRLS weight for observation i at residual-model iteration t .	§6.3
$\hat{y}_i^{(k)}$	Out-of-fold prediction for observation i in fold/cross combination k . Variance over k estimates <code>modvar_i</code> .	§6.3

B Glossary of Code Symbols and Implementation Terms

This appendix lists the R-level functions, object fields, arguments, and ancillary functions used in the pseudocode and body text. All names are as they appear in the CRAN `earth` package (version 5.3.5 at time of writing).

Public functions (what you call)

Name	Role
<code>earth()</code>	Top-level entry point. Accepts a formula or (x, y) , fits a MARS model, optionally with cross-validation or a GLM family.
<code>summary.earth()</code>	Prints the fitted equation, coefficients, and fit statistics. Use <code>style = "pmax"</code> for cleaner hinge notation.
<code>format.earth()</code>	Returns the fitted equation as an R expression.
<code>plot.earth()</code>	Four diagnostic plots: model-selection (GCV/RSq vs. size), residual CDF, residuals vs. fitted, QQ.
<code>plotmo()</code>	Plots the fitted function against each predictor, holding others at their medians. Available in a separate companion package with the same name.
<code>evimp()</code>	Variable-importance rankings by <code>nsubsets</code> , GCV, and RSS criteria.
<code>predict.earth()</code>	Predictions on new data. Supports <code>type = "response"</code> , <code>"link"</code> , <code>"earth"</code> , <code>"class"</code> , <code>"terms"</code> , and when a variance model is present the <code>interval</code> argument with values <code>"pint"</code> , <code>"cint"</code> , <code>"se"</code> .
<code>model.matrix.earth()</code>	Evaluates <code>bx</code> on new data. Used to hand the basis to downstream packages such as <code>glmnet</code> .
<code>update.earth()</code>	Refits with modified arguments; fast when <code>keepxy = TRUE</code> .
<code>varmod()</code>	Low-level constructor for a variance model. End users normally obtain a variance model by passing <code>varmod.method</code> to <code>earth()</code> rather than calling <code>varmod()</code> directly.
<code>summary.varmod()</code>	Prints the variance model: method, coefficients with standard errors, <code>iter.rsq</code> , prediction-interval widths, coverage table. Called indirectly by <code>summary.earth()</code> .
<code>plot.varmod()</code>	Four-panel diagnostic for the variance model: absolute residuals vs fitted, absolute residuals vs first predictor, residual-model residuals, and (for <code>varmod.method = "earth"</code>) a model-selection plot.

Name	Role
<code>predict.varmod()</code>	Invoked internally by <code>predict.earth()</code> when <code>interval</code> is specified; handles the leverage correction, the 1.2533 rescaling, and the <code>min.sd</code> clamp.
<code>mars.to.earth()</code>	Converts an <code>mda::mars</code> object to an <code>earth</code> object.

Internal layers (what gets called)

Name	Role
<code>earth.fit()</code>	Orchestrator. Calls <code>forward.pass</code> and <code>pruning.pass</code> , runs the final OLS, assembles the return object.
<code>forward.pass()</code>	Greedy basis construction. Most of the runtime lives here. Heavily implemented in C.
<code>pruning.pass()</code>	Backward elimination (default) or all-subsets via <code>leaps</code> .
<code>get.bx()</code>	Evaluates the stored basis on new data using <code>dirs</code> and <code>cuts</code> .
<code>get.gcv()</code>	Computes the GCV statistic from RSS, number of terms, penalty, and N .
<code>effective.nbr.of.params()</code>	Computes $C(M) = M + d \cdot K$ for a candidate model.
<code>hatvalues_qr()</code>	Computes leverages (diagonal of the hat matrix).

Common `earth()` arguments

Argument	Meaning and default
<code>formula / x, y</code>	Model specification. Formula interface or <code>x</code> matrix and <code>y</code> vector.
<code>weights</code>	Case weights; NULL means unweighted.
<code>wp</code>	Response weights for multi-response models; NULL means unweighted.
<code>subset</code>	Row indices to fit on.
<code>na.action</code>	Only <code>na.fail</code> is supported.
<code>degree</code>	Maximum interaction degree. Default 1 (additive).
<code>nk</code>	Maximum basis functions. Default $\min(200, \max(20, 2p)) + 1$.

Argument	Meaning and default
<code>penalty</code>	GCV penalty per knot d . Default 2 if <code>degree = 1</code> , else 3. Special values: 0 (penalize only terms), -1 (no penalty).
<code>thresh</code>	Forward-pass RSS-reduction threshold. Default 10^{-3} .
<code>minspan</code>	Min obs between knots. Default 0 (auto-selected).
<code>endspan</code>	Min obs before/after end knots. Default 0 (auto-selected).
<code>fast.k</code>	Fast MARS parent cap. Default 20. 0 disables Fast MARS.
<code>fast.beta</code>	Fast MARS ageing coefficient. Default 1.
<code>pmethod</code>	Pruning method: "backward" (default), "none", "exhaustive", "forward", "seqrep", "cv".
<code>nprune</code>	Max terms after pruning. Default NULL (no cap beyond the pruning-pass selection).
<code>nfold</code>	Number of CV folds. Default 0 (no CV).
<code>ncross</code>	Number of CV replications. Default 1.
<code>stratify</code>	Stratify CV folds on the response. Default TRUE.
<code>glm</code>	Optional list of <code>glm()</code> arguments to post-fit a GLM on <code>bx</code> .
<code>linpreds</code>	Which predictors enter linearly (no hinge). Default FALSE.
<code>allowed</code>	Function controlling which interactions are allowed.
<code>keepxy</code>	If TRUE, retain <code>x</code> and <code>y</code> in the returned object (needed for efficient <code>update.earth</code>).
<code>trace</code>	Verbosity: 0, 0.3, 0.5, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5.
<code>varmod.method</code>	Variance-model method for prediction intervals. Default "none". See the <code>varmod.method</code> values table below for allowed values.
<code>varmod.exponent</code>	Power transform applied to \hat{y} before the variance-model regression (e.g., 0.5 for square root). Default 1. Used when you know the theoretical power but want an <code>lm</code> fit.
<code>varmod.conv</code>	IRLS convergence criterion, in percent change of coefficients. Default 1. Negative values force a fixed iteration count.
<code>varmod.clamp</code>	Multiplier for <code>min.sd</code> ; the minimum standard deviation allowed is <code>varmod.clamp</code> \times mean training residual SD. Default 0.1.
<code>varmod.minspan</code>	<code>minspan</code> used in the internal <code>earth</code> call when <code>varmod.method = "earth"</code> or <code>"x.earth"</code> . Default -3 (three evenly spaced knots per predictor).

varmod.method values

Value	Meaning
"none"	Default. No variance model is built. Prediction intervals are not available.
"const"	Assume homoscedastic errors (constant variance). No residual regression; $\hat{\sigma}$ is a scalar.
"lm"	Linear regression of absolute residuals on fitted values. Recommended default when intervals are wanted.
"rlm"	Robust linear regression via <code>MASS::rlm</code> . Narrower intervals; can underestimate variance on Gaussian-like data.
"earth"	Use a MARS fit for the residual model. Captures nonlinear variance patterns. Uses <code>varmod.minspan</code> .
"gam"	Use a GAM fit (<code>gam</code> or <code>mgcv::gam</code> , whichever is loaded).
"power"	Power-of-the-mean model: $\hat{\sigma} = \text{intercept} + \text{coef} \cdot \hat{y}^{\text{exp}}$. Exponent is estimated.
"power0"	Same as "power" but without intercept.
"x.lm"	Linear regression of absolute residuals on the <i>predictors</i> X rather than \hat{y} . Use for multimapped variance (§6.7).
"x.rlm"	Robust version of "x.lm".
"x.earth"	MARS fit on predictors.
"x.gam"	GAM fit on predictors. Implementation restriction: currently one predictor only.

Fit-object fields

A fitted `earth` object is an S3 list. The most important fields for downstream use are:

Field	Meaning
<code>bx</code>	Basis matrix evaluated on training data, $N \times M$. Columns correspond to <code>selected.terms</code> .
<code>dirs</code>	$M \times p$ direction matrix. Entry $(m, j) \in \{-1, 0, 1, 2\}$ encodes predictor j 's role in term m (see §4.2).
<code>cuts</code>	$M \times p$ matrix of knot locations. Zero where <code>dirs</code> is 0 or 2.
<code>selected.terms</code>	Indices (into the forward-pass basis) of terms retained after pruning.
<code>coefficients</code>	OLS coefficient matrix, one column per response. First row is the intercept.

Field	Meaning
<code>fitted.values</code>	Fitted \hat{y} on the training data.
<code>residuals</code>	$y - \hat{y}$ on the training data.
<code>rss</code>	Residual sum of squares of the selected model.
<code>rsq</code>	In-sample R-squared.
<code>gcv</code>	GCV of the selected model.
<code>gcv.null</code>	GCV of the intercept-only model. Used to compute <code>grsq</code> .
<code>grsq</code>	$1 - \text{gcv}/\text{gcv.null}$. GCV analogue of R-squared. Can be negative for severely over-parameterized models.
<code>rss.per.subset</code>	RSS of each model size visited by the pruning pass.
<code>gcv.per.subset</code>	GCV of each such sub-model.
<code>prune.terms</code>	Lower-triangular matrix recording which terms are in each sub-model. Row k lists terms in the best k -term model.
<code>leverages</code>	Diagonal h_{ii} of the hat matrix H . Used by the variance model.
<code>penalty</code>	Copy of the <code>penalty</code> argument used.
<code>nk,</code> <code>thresh,</code> <code>pmethod</code>	Copies of the corresponding arguments.
<code>termcond</code>	Integer code for why the forward pass terminated.
<code>call</code>	Original user call.
<code>terms</code>	Formula model-frame terms (when the formula interface was used).
<code>glm.list</code>	Present only if <code>glm = list(...)</code> was supplied. List of <code>glm</code> fits, one per response.
<code>cv.rsq.tab,</code> <code>cv.oof.rsq.tab</code>	Cross-validation results, present only if <code>nfold > 0</code> .
<code>varmod</code>	Present only if <code>varmod.method</code> was specified and not "none". See the <code>varmod</code> sub-object fields table below.

varmod sub-object fields

Available as `earth.mod$varmod`.

Field	Meaning
<code>method</code>	Copy of <code>varmod.method</code> .
<code>residmod</code>	The residual sub-model itself (an <code>lm</code> , <code>rlm</code> , <code>earth</code> , <code>gam</code> , or <code>nls</code> object, depending on <code>method</code>).

Field	Meaning
<code>min.sd</code>	The clamping floor σ_{\min} for estimated standard deviations.
<code>iter.rsq</code>	R^2 of the residual sub-model at the final IRLS iteration. Indicator of how much signal the variance model extracted.
<code>iter.stderr</code>	Standard errors of the residual-model coefficients at the final IRLS iteration. Printed in <code>summary.earth</code> output.
<code>iters</code>	Number of IRLS iterations performed.
<code>converged</code>	Logical; whether IRLS converged before hitting its iteration cap.
<code>abs.resids</code>	The leverage-corrected absolute residuals that were regressed against.
<code>model.var</code>	Per-observation model-variance estimate from cross-validation.
<code>parent.call</code>	The original <code>earth()</code> call; used in plot titles.

`predict.earth()` interval values

Value	Meaning
<code>"pint"</code>	Prediction interval. The default when a variance model is present. Uses leverage correction + model variance + 1.2533 rescaling + normal-theory interval.
<code>"cint"</code>	Confidence interval (for the mean response). Uses only the model-variance term. Not allowed with <code>newdata</code> .
<code>"se"</code>	Standard errors only, no interval bounds.

Pruning methods (values of `pmethod`)

Value	Meaning
<code>"backward"</code>	Default. Nested backward elimination guided by RSS, with final selection by GCV.
<code>"none"</code>	Retain all forward-pass terms. Useful for diagnostic comparisons.
<code>"exhaustive"</code>	True all-subsets search via <code>leaps</code> . Expensive for models with more than about 30 terms.

Value	Meaning
"forward"	Forward stepwise on the set of forward-pass terms. Rarely used.
"seqrep"	Sequential replacement. Rarely used.
"cv"	Select number of terms by cross-validated out-of-fold RSq. Requires <code>nfold > 0</code> .

Hinge-term notation in printed output

Notation	Meaning
$h(x - t)$ or $\text{pmax}(x - t, 0)$	Right-side hinge: $(x - t)_+$.
$h(t - x)$ or $\text{pmax}(t - x, 0)$	Left-side hinge: $(t - x)_+$.
$h(\text{GLA-1820}) * h(\text{Age-15})$	Degree-2 interaction term.
(Intercept)	The constant basis function $B_0 \equiv 1$.

Factor handling

Name	Role
<code>contr.earth.response</code>	Identity-contrasts function used to expand a multi-level factor <i>response</i> into k indicator columns. Differs from standard R contrasts such as <code>contr.treatment</code> ; see §5.4.
<code>contr.treatment</code>	Standard R treatment contrast used to expand multi-level factor <i>predictors</i> into $k - 1$ indicator columns, with the first level held out as the reference.
<code>Auto.linpreds</code>	<code>earth()</code> argument (default TRUE). Detects 0/1 columns and enters them linearly rather than via a degenerate hinge. Controls how indicator columns appear in the <code>dirs</code> matrix (entry 2 rather than ± 1).
<code>linpreds</code>	<code>earth()</code> argument. Explicit override: names or indices of predictors that should enter linearly regardless of whether <code>Auto.linpreds</code> detects them.

Name	Role
<code>stratify</code>	<code>earth()</code> argument (default <code>TRUE</code> when <code>nfold > 0</code>). Stratifies CV folds on the response. Important for factor responses; does not stratify on factor predictors.
<code>namesx</code>	Optional <code>earth()</code> argument. Column names of <code>x</code> after factor expansion. Used by the <code>allowed</code> function to refer to predictors by name.

C Glossary of Statistical Terms

This appendix defines statistical terminology used throughout the document. Entries are in alphabetical order. They are working definitions aimed at an appraiser with a background in mathematics; a standard reference such as Hastie, Tibshirani, and Friedman's *Elements of Statistical Learning* should be consulted for precise statements and proofs.

Term	Definition
Additive model	A model in which the effect of each predictor enters as its own term, with no interaction between predictors. The output is a sum of one-variable functions. Equivalent in <code>earth</code> to <code>degree = 1</code> .
Basis function	One of a set of functions $\{B_1, B_2, \dots\}$ whose linear combination constitutes the fitted model. In MARS the basis functions are hinge functions and products of hinges.
Bias	The systematic component of error: how far off the fitted function is, <i>on average</i> , from the true underlying relationship. Contrast with variance.
Bias–variance tradeoff	The observation that more flexible models (more terms, more knots, smaller penalties) reduce bias but increase variance, and vice versa. Good model selection seeks the minimum of the sum.
Binomial	A probability distribution for the number of successes in a fixed number of independent 0/1 trials. The <code>family = binomial</code> case in a GLM models a 0/1 or proportion response; logistic regression is its most common form.
Collinearity	Near-linear dependence among predictor columns. Produces unstable coefficient estimates; hinge bases from <code>earth</code> are typically quite collinear because neighboring knots generate correlated columns.

Term	Definition
Confidence interval	An interval around the predicted <i>mean response</i> at a given predictor configuration. Narrower than a prediction interval because it does not include the irreducible-noise component.
Convex (function, problem)	A function is convex if every line segment between two points on its graph lies on or above the graph. A convex optimization problem has no local minima other than the global one, making it easy to solve. Elastic-net regression is convex; MARS basis selection is not.
Cox model	A semi-parametric model for survival (time-to-event) data. The <code>family = "cox"</code> case in <code>glmnet</code> and <code>earth</code> . Rarely used in appraisal.
Cross-validation (k-fold)	An out-of-sample performance estimate. The data are split into k folds; the model is fit on $k - 1$ folds and evaluated on the held-out fold; the process cycles through all k folds and averages the results. $k = 10$ is the customary default.
Degrees of freedom	Loosely, the effective number of parameters a model uses. For ordinary linear regression with p predictors and an intercept, the degrees of freedom are $p + 1$. For more flexible models (including MARS), the effective degrees of freedom can exceed the apparent parameter count because the model “spends” degrees of freedom in basis selection.
Deviance	A generalization of residual sum of squares to GLMs: twice the difference in log-likelihood between the fitted model and the saturated model (the one that fits every observation exactly). For Gaussian regression, deviance equals RSS.
Dummy variable	Synonym for indicator column: a 0/1 numeric column representing membership in a category.
Effective degrees of freedom	See degrees of freedom. In MARS, the $C(M) = M + d \cdot K$ expression used inside the GCV formula is an effective-degrees-of-freedom count that charges the model for knot selection in addition to term selection.
Gaussian	The normal distribution. The default family for <code>earth</code> and for <code>glmnet</code> with continuous-response regression.

Term	Definition
Generalized linear model (GLM)	A regression framework that replaces the Gaussian error model with an arbitrary distribution (binomial, Poisson, etc.) plus a link function. The mean response is modeled as $g^{-1}(x^\top \beta)$ where g is the link.
Hat matrix	The $N \times N$ matrix H satisfying $\hat{y} = Hy$ for a linear regression. Its diagonal entries h_{ii} are the leverages.
Heteroscedasticity	Error variance that depends on the predictors or the fitted value — not constant across observations. Common in price data, where expensive properties typically show wider absolute residuals than cheap ones. Greek roots: <i>hetero</i> (different) + <i>skedastikos</i> (able to disperse).
Hinge function	A one-sided linear function of a predictor, zero on one side of a knot and linear on the other: $(x - t)_+$ or $(t - x)_+$. The building block of MARS.
Homoscedasticity	Error variance that is constant across observations. The assumption of standard linear regression. Greek for “same scatter.”
Identity link	The degenerate link function $g(\mu) = \mu$. Gaussian regression uses the identity link.
Indicator column (indicator variable)	A 0/1 numeric column signaling presence or absence of a category. Factors with k levels expand to k or $k - 1$ indicator columns depending on contrast convention.
Interaction	A term in the model that combines two or more predictors multiplicatively, capturing the case where the effect of one predictor depends on the value of another. In MARS, an interaction is a product of hinge functions in different predictors.
IRLS (iteratively reweighted least squares)	An algorithm for fitting non-Gaussian GLMs: at each step, build a local quadratic approximation to the log-likelihood, solve it as a weighted least-squares problem, update the fit, and iterate. <code>glmnet</code> uses this for non-Gaussian families; <code>earth</code> uses it inside the variance model.
Knot	The scalar t inside a hinge function $(x - t)_+$ or $(t - x)_+$. Geometrically, the point at which the piecewise-linear function changes slope.
Leave-one-out cross-validation (LOOCV)	k -fold cross-validation in the limit $k = N$: each fold is a single observation. Prohibitively expensive to compute directly for most models, but approximated efficiently by GCV for linear smoothers.

Term	Definition
Leverage	A measure of how much a single observation influences its own fitted value. Equal to the hat-matrix diagonal h_{ii} ; always between 0 and 1; averages to p/N . High leverage points are typically at the edges of the predictor space.
Likelihood / log-likelihood	The probability of the observed data under a candidate model, as a function of the model parameters. Log-likelihood is its logarithm, used for numerical stability. Maximum likelihood estimation picks the parameter vector that maximizes the (log-)likelihood.
Link function	In a GLM, the function g relating the linear predictor to the mean response: $g(\mu_i) = \eta_i$. Common choices: identity (Gaussian), logit (binomial), log (Poisson).
MARS (Multi-variate Adaptive Regression Splines)	Friedman's nonparametric regression method implemented in the <code>earth</code> package. Models a response as a sum of hinge basis functions discovered by a forward/backward greedy search.
Model variance	The variance of the fitted value at a fixed predictor configuration, across repeated training samples. Not the same as residual variance. Estimated via cross-validation in <code>earth</code> 's variance model.
Normal approximation	Treating a quantity whose exact distribution is complicated as if it were normally distributed, justified by the central limit theorem or by similar asymptotic results. Used in interval construction via $z_{\alpha/2}$.
OLS (ordinary least squares)	Regression fit by minimizing the unweighted sum of squared residuals. The final coefficient estimation step in <code>earth</code> ; also what standard <code>lm()</code> performs.
Overfitting	Fitting noise rather than signal: the model performs much better on the training data than on new data. <code>earth</code> 's forward pass deliberately overfits; the backward pass then corrects it.
Penalized regression	Regression that adds a penalty term to the squared-error objective, discouraging large coefficient values or large model complexity. <code>glmnet</code> 's elastic net is one example; GCV-guided pruning in <code>earth</code> is another.
Poisson	A distribution for count data (non-negative integers). The <code>family = poisson</code> case in GLMs, with the log link function. Rare in appraisal except for event-count sub-problems.

Term	Definition
Prediction interval	An interval around the prediction for a single future observation. Wider than a confidence interval at the same level, because it includes both model variance and irreducible-error variance. The appropriate object for reporting an appraisal value range.
QR decomposition	A matrix factorization $X = QR$ with Q orthogonal and R upper triangular. The numerically stable workhorse for least-squares regression; used inside earth and inside the leaps subset-search routine.
Quantile	A value below which a specified fraction of a distribution lies. The 0.975 quantile of the standard normal distribution, $z_{0.025} = 1.96$, appears in 95% interval construction.
Residual	The difference between an observed and fitted value: $\hat{\epsilon}_i = y_i - \hat{y}_i$. Raw residuals underestimate the errors a model would make on new data; leverage correction accounts for this.
R-squared (RSq)	(R^2) , The fraction of total response variance explained by the fitted model: $1 - \text{RSS}/\text{TSS}$. Always in $[0, 1]$ for ordinary least squares. Analogues GRSq and CVRSq substitute GCV and cross-validated RSS for the in-sample RSS.
RSS (residual sum of squares)	$\sum_i (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2$. The core training-error measure for squared-loss regression.
Saturated model	A model with one parameter per observation, fitting the data exactly. The upper bound against which deviance is measured.
Skewness	Asymmetry of a distribution. A symmetric distribution has zero skewness; a long right tail has positive skewness. earth 's variance model assumes roughly symmetric residuals.
Sparsity	The property that most coefficients in a fitted model are exactly zero. Lasso induces sparsity; MARS can produce it through pruning.
Stratified sampling	Splitting data so that some feature of the response (or a predictor) has approximately the same distribution in every subset. earth 's stratify = TRUE argument stratifies CV folds on a categorical response.
Variance (as model quantity)	The expected squared deviation of an estimate from its own expected value. The variability component of error, as opposed to bias.

Term	Definition
Weighted least squares (WLS)	Least-squares regression with observations weighted unequally: $\min \sum_i w_i (y_i - x_i^\top \beta)^2$. Appears in IRLS as the inner subproblem after the quadratic approximation of a GLM log-likelihood.
$z_{\alpha/2}$	The quantile of the standard normal distribution leaving $\alpha/2$ probability in each tail. $z_{0.025} = 1.96$ for a 95% two-sided interval.

D Numerical Linear Algebra Background

This appendix expands on the QR decomposition introduced in §3.5. The main-body subsection covered the *use* of the factorization — what QR accomplishes and why it is the right tool for least squares on the hinge basis. This appendix covers the *mechanics* — how the factorization is actually computed, and why the two standard methods, Householder reflections and Givens rotations, are stable in ways that classical Gram-Schmidt orthogonalization is not.

D.1 The QR decomposition, restated

For a matrix X of size $N \times k$ with $N \geq k$ and full column rank, the QR factorization writes

$$X = QR,$$

where Q is $N \times k$ with orthonormal columns ($Q^\top Q = I_k$) and R is $k \times k$ upper triangular with positive diagonal. Two things about this factorization are worth emphasizing. First, it is unique given the positive-diagonal convention on R . Second, any algorithm that produces Q and R satisfying these properties (exactly or to working precision) is a valid implementation; the choice of algorithm affects numerical behavior but not the mathematical result.

Three families of algorithms are in common use:

- **Classical (and modified) Gram-Schmidt:** build Q column-by-column by subtracting projections onto previously computed columns and normalizing.
- **Householder reflections:** build R by reflecting the columns of X onto coordinate axes, one column at a time. Q is the product of the reflections, stored implicitly.
- **Givens rotations:** build R by rotating pairs of rows in the (x_i, x_j) -plane to zero out one subdiagonal entry at a time. Q is the product of the rotations.

Householder and Givens are dramatically more stable than Gram-Schmidt on ill-conditioned matrices such as the hinge-basis matrices MARS produces. The remainder of this appendix explains why, starting with a geometric description of what each method does.

D.2 Householder reflections: zero a column by one mirror-flip

The Householder approach operates one column of X at a time. Given a vector $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$, the goal is to transform x into a vector that points purely along the first coordinate axis $e_1 = (1, 0, \dots, 0)^\top$, while preserving length. The target is αe_1 where $|\alpha| = \|x\|$.

Geometrically, the transformation that accomplishes this in one step is a *reflection*. The reflection plane bisects the angle between x and its target αe_1 . If $v = x - \alpha e_1$ is the vector from the target to the starting point, then the plane perpendicular to v is exactly the plane that reflects x onto αe_1 . The matrix of this reflection is

$$H = I - \frac{2vv^\top}{v^\top v}.$$

Geometrically, H acts on any input by decomposing it into its component along v and its component perpendicular to v ; it flips the along- v component and leaves the perpendicular part alone. Standard reflection across a hyperplane.

Applied to x by construction, $Hx = \alpha e_1$: every entry of x below the first has been zeroed out by one reflection. The full QR algorithm applies this column-by-column: the first reflection zeros out column 1 below the diagonal; the second reflection (acting on the $(n-1) \times (n-1)$ lower-right submatrix) zeros out column 2 below the diagonal; and so on. After k reflections the matrix has been reduced to upper triangular form R , and the product of the reflections (each of which is exactly orthogonal) is Q^\top .

In practice Q is not stored explicitly. Instead the vectors v_1, v_2, \dots, v_k used to construct each reflection are stored, and applications of Q or Q^\top are computed on the fly by applying the reflections in sequence. This makes Householder QR dense-efficient: one reflection zeros out many entries at once, and its cost is proportional to the number of entries it touches.

D.3 Givens rotations: spin two coordinates until one becomes zero

Givens takes a different tactic: zero out one entry at a time by rotating two rows.

Consider a vector $(a, b)^\top$ in \mathbb{R}^2 . Rotating by the angle θ with

$$\cos \theta = \frac{a}{\sqrt{a^2 + b^2}}, \quad \sin \theta = \frac{b}{\sqrt{a^2 + b^2}}$$

produces a new vector $(\sqrt{a^2 + b^2}, 0)^\top$: the second entry has been rotated to zero. The rotation matrix is

$$G = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta & \sin \theta \\ -\sin \theta & \cos \theta \end{pmatrix}.$$

This lifts to \mathbb{R}^n by embedding the 2×2 rotation in the identity matrix at rows i and j , producing a matrix G_{ij} that rotates the (x_i, x_j) -plane and leaves the other $n-2$ coordinates fixed. Apply G_{ij} from the left to a matrix X , and rows i and j of X are mixed by the rotation while all other rows are unchanged. Choose the angle so that the application zeros out one specific entry — typically the subdiagonal entry you are trying to eliminate.

To produce a QR factorization, walk through the subdiagonal entries of X one at a time. For each nonzero subdiagonal entry, construct a Givens rotation that zeros it out by mixing

that row with the row above. After every subdiagonal entry has been zeroed, the remaining matrix is R , and the product of the rotations is Q^\top .

Givens QR is less efficient than Householder for dense full factorizations — each rotation zeros a single entry rather than many at once. Where Givens shines is in *updating*: when the matrix changes by a rank-one perturbation (for example, a single column changing in only a few entries, as happens in the knot search of §3.6), a short sequence of Givens rotations can transform the old R into the new one in $O(Nk)$ operations. For the same problem, recomputing a Householder factorization from scratch would cost $O(Nk^2)$. This is why **earth**'s C implementation uses Givens rotations for the knot-search and pruning-pass updates specifically.

D.4 Why these are stable and Gram-Schmidt is not

Classical Gram-Schmidt (CGS) builds Q by arithmetic: project column x_k of X onto each previously-constructed q_1, \dots, q_{k-1} , subtract the projections, and normalize the result to produce q_k . Algebraically, if X has linearly independent columns, this reproduces Q exactly. In floating-point arithmetic, it does not.

The failure mode of CGS is *catastrophic cancellation*. Each inner product $q_j^\top x_k$ is computed with a rounding error of roughly $\varepsilon_{\text{machine}} \|q_j\| \|x_k\|$. When x_k is nearly in the span of q_1, \dots, q_{k-1} — which happens precisely when the columns of X are strongly correlated, as with the hinge basis — the subtraction $q'_k = x_k - \sum_j (q_j^\top x_k) q_j$ is the small difference of large, nearly-equal quantities. Most of the significant digits of q'_k cancel, and the small residual that remains is dominated by accumulated rounding error. The claim “the computed q_j 's are orthonormal” then fails numerically: $Q^\top Q \neq I$ in the computed result, sometimes badly.

Standard backward-error analysis shows that the loss of orthogonality in CGS grows roughly as $\kappa(X)^2 \varepsilon_{\text{machine}}$, where $\kappa(X)$ is the condition number of X . For the seven-column hinge basis of §3.5 with $\kappa(X) \approx 10^4$, that is $10^8 \times \varepsilon \approx 10^{-8}$ in double precision — eight digits lost, eight digits kept. For a larger MARS problem with $\kappa(X) \approx 10^7$, CGS would produce a Q that is essentially not orthogonal at all.

Householder and Givens sidestep this failure mode entirely. A Householder reflection $H = I - 2vv^\top / (v^\top v)$ satisfies $H^\top H = I$ as a *mathematical identity*, not as a computation. Evaluating H in floating-point produces a matrix whose orthogonality is correct to within a few multiples of $\varepsilon_{\text{machine}}$, regardless of the input vector's magnitude or the condition of the problem. The same is true of Givens rotations: $G^\top G = I$ by algebra.

The key distinction is that Householder and Givens construct Q by *transformation* using operators that are mathematically orthogonal by their construction, while Gram-Schmidt constructs Q by *subtraction* using projections whose rounding errors compound. Orthogonality in the first approach is a property of the operator; in the second, it is a property of the arithmetic.

The standard stability result (Wilkinson) is that Householder QR produces computed factors \hat{Q}, \hat{R} satisfying

$$\hat{Q}\hat{R} = X + E, \quad \|E\| \lesssim k \varepsilon_{\text{machine}} \|X\|,$$

with $\|\hat{Q}^\top \hat{Q} - I\| \lesssim k \varepsilon_{\text{machine}}$ — *independent of $\kappa(X)$* . Givens has the same guarantee. For

the seven-column hinge basis, both methods produce Q that is orthogonal to roughly 10^{-15} in double precision, not 10^{-8} .

D.5 Summary

Method	Loss of orthogonality	Typical use
Classical Gram-Schmidt	$\sim \kappa(X)^2 \varepsilon$	Avoid for serious work
Modified Gram-Schmidt	$\sim \kappa(X) \varepsilon$	Tolerable, occasional
Householder reflections	$\sim k \varepsilon$	Dense full factorization
Givens rotations	$\sim k \varepsilon$	Updates, sparse, structured

For the operations that matter in `earth`:

- The *initial* QR factorization of `bx` is computed by Householder reflections (this is what LINPACK’s `dqrdc`, LAPACK’s `dgeqrf`, and R’s `qr()` use under the hood).
- The *incremental updates* during the knot search and pruning-pass deletions are computed by Givens rotations, which are natural for one-entry-at-a-time modifications.

The reader who wants to see this machinery at work in source can consult the C routines `ForwardPass` and `OrderFold` in `earth.c`, which call into BLAS/LAPACK for the dense Householder step and implement their own Givens updates for the incremental passes. Trefethen and Bau’s *Numerical Linear Algebra* is the standard reference for the stability analyses; Golub and Van Loan’s *Matrix Computations* is the more encyclopedic source.

References

- [1] Craytor, B. (2026). *earthUI: A Shiny Graphical User Interface for the earth Package*. R package, CRAN version 0.1.3; development version on GitHub. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=earthUI>. <https://github.com/wcraytor/earthUI>.
- [2] Craytor, B. (2026). *glmnetUI: A Shiny Graphical User Interface for the glmnet Package*. R package, development version. <https://github.com/wcraytor/glmnetUI>.
- [3] Craytor, B. (2026). *mgcvUI: A Shiny Graphical User Interface for the mgcv Package*. R package, development version. <https://github.com/wcraytor/mgcvUI>.
- [4] Friedman, J. H. (1991). Multivariate adaptive regression splines. *The Annals of Statistics*, 19(1):1–141.
- [5] Hastie, T., Tibshirani, R., and Friedman, J. H. (2017). *The Elements of Statistical Learning: Data Mining, Inference, and Prediction*. Springer Series in Statistics. Springer, New York, 2nd edition.

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- [6] James, G., Witten, D., Hastie, T., and Tibshirani, R. (2021). *An Introduction to Statistical Learning: With Applications in R*. Springer Texts in Statistics. Springer, New York, 2nd edition.
- [7] Krivorotov, G. and LaCour-Little, M. (2020). AVM versus appraisal-based underwriting in refinance mortgages: The trade-off between noise and bias. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3603327>.
- [8] Kuhn, M. and Johnson, K. (2016). *Applied Predictive Modeling*. Springer, New York, 5th corrected printing.
- [9] Milborrow, S. (2026). Notes on the earth package. Package vignette, January 2026. <http://www.milbo.org/doc/earth-notes.pdf>.
- [10] Milborrow, S. (2026). Variance models in earth. Package vignette, January 2026. <http://www.milbo.org/doc/earth-varmod.pdf>.
- [11] Milborrow, S. (2026). *earth: Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines*. R package version 5.3.5. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=earth>.
- [12] Tzioumis, K. (2016). Appraisers and valuation bias: An empirical analysis. *Real Estate Economics*, 45(3):679–712. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1540-6229.12133>.
- [13] Zhang, W. (2020). *MARS Applications in Geotechnical Engineering Systems: Multi-Dimension with Big Data*. Springer, Singapore.